

國立臺灣大學理學院化學研究所

博士論文

Graduate Institute of Chemistry

College of Science

National Taiwan University

Doctoral Dissertation

合成不對稱之複雜型 *N* 型多醣骨架

以為酵素促進多樣化與功能性研究

Synthesis of Asymmetric Complex Type *N*-Glycan Structures as
Common Core Substrates for Diversification through Selective
Enzymatic Glycosylation

許立

Li Hsu

指導教授：翁啟惠 博士

Advisor: Chi-Huey Wong, Ph.D.

中華民國 109 年 12 月

December, 2020

謝誌

經過了日以繼夜的實驗與埋首案牘的撰寫，這份多醣合成化學的工作終於進入了尾聲。在漫長的研究生歲月中，首先要感謝恩師翁啟惠老師的指引。從多次的討論乃至於激勵與生活上的關懷，以及充分的自由發揮的空間，讓我得以在這學術的茫茫大海中找到方向，並且一步一步地完成這份工作，這些都讓學生感到無比感激。

在論文寫作方面，幸得吳宗益老師、方俊民老師、蒙國光老師與謝俊結老師四位口試委員的嚴格指導，使我得以專業與條理地呈現我的研究成果，並使我充分的認識了從事研究工作所必須要有的視野與整合能力。因為這些諄諄教誨，我才能順利完成這份論文，對此特表感謝。

在實驗的部分，我特別要感謝靖軒與郁瑋的鼎力協助，因為這樣我才能完成研究的最後一塊拼圖。當然還得感謝我的重要的合作夥伴 Sujeet Pawar，我們的分工雖非摧枯拉朽但也是滴水穿石金石為開。另外還要感謝子文學長還有翠玲學姊，除了獲得裨益良多的意見之外，也讓我對科學研究實踐有了更深刻的認知與體悟。我也必須感謝 Sachin Shivatare，讓我在初進實驗室中能夠站穩腳步。還要感謝信佑學長、政越學長與宏揚學長的技巧傳授與各種解惑，讓我最終能獨當一面。

除此之外，我要感謝來自同儕鼓舞與關心，讓我在徬徨與枯乾的邊緣能夠找回推進的動力。在此向一路以來相挺的逸翔，一同橫越心靈自由的大陸的業康、仔君，不時捎來關心的葉博士、翊偉學長、漢文學長、建有學長，在關鍵時刻伸出援手的彥文，互相勉勵打氣的志浩、哲群、惠中、佩庭、乃瑜、雨萱、采容獻上最誠摯的謝意。

在最後，要感謝我的母親與父親，默默的支持我多年求學生涯。還有我的弟弟與妹妹，你們的陪伴是我的支柱。

Jan 27, 2021 書於水返腳社后

獻給山貓，那穿越遙遠深邃宇宙的幽暗星光

中文摘要

位於醣蛋白(glycoprotein)上之 *N*型多醣(*N*-glycan)具有結構多樣化、位置異構物眾多並且在不同的生物機轉中具備特定功能之特性。然而 *N*型多醣之異構物也具有難以個別分離與鑑定之特性，同時它們更加細節的作用機轉原理尚未被徹底了解。這方面主要肇因於缺乏有效取得均質(homogeneous)特定異構物樣本之方法，特別是對於結構不對稱之 *N*型多醣。當前取得 *N*型多醣樣本的方法主要為化學合成法或化學酵素合成(chemo-enzymatic synthesis)法。前者倚賴複雜的保護基轉換與繁瑣的中間體純化；後者的瓶頸則在於酵素的可得性、反應的轉換率不完全以及仍然需要適當的引介保護基以進行位置選擇的酵素反應。本研究內容在於開發一個改進的不對稱 *N*型多醣樣本之合成策略。此策略的核心在於先透過化學合成取得一個較簡單的中間體，並透過這個中間體再進行酵素醣化以得到具有岩藻醣基(fucosyl)或是唾液酸基(*N*-acetylneuraminy)之不對稱 *N*型多醣。

關鍵字：醣類、寡糖、化學醣基化、酵素醣基化、岩藻醣化、唾液酸化

ABSTRACT

N-glycans on glycoproteins are structurally diverse, containing numerous regio-isomers with different roles in biological processes, such as immune signaling and disease progressions. However, these isomers are difficult to distinguish and their detailed functions are still not well understood mainly due to the lack of effective methods for access to these structures in pure form. Current access to complex type *N*-glycans is mainly through chemical or chemo-enzymatic synthesis; the former involves complex protecting group manipulation and intermediate purification, and the later often encounters problems of enzyme availability, incomplete reaction and requires introduction of protecting groups to avoid unwanted enzymatic glycosylation. We have developed an improved strategy for asymmetric *N*-glycan assembly and diversification using a common and versatile core substrate without protecting group for selective enzymatic fucosylation and sialylation.

Keywords: Carbohydrate/ Oligosaccharide/ Chemical glycosylation/ Enzymatic glycosylation/ Fucosylation/ Sialylation

CONTENTS

中文摘要	i
ABSTRACT.....	ii
CONTENTS	iii
LIST OF FIGURES	v
LIST of SCHEMES	vi
LIST of Charts	vii
ABBREVIATIONS	viii
Chapter 1 Introduction	1
Chapter 2 Results and Discussion.....	8
2.1 Retrosynthetic Analysis.....	8
2.2 Synthesis of the Monosaccharide Building Blocks.....	12
2.3 Synthesis of the Disaccharide without Galactose.....	14
2.4 Synthesis of the Galactose bearing Tetrasaccharide.....	15
2.5 Synthesis of the core trisaccharide.....	17
2.6 Installation of the tetrasaccharide on core.....	17
2.7 Installation of the disaccharide and global deprotection.....	20
2.8 Enzymatic Glycosylation.....	21
2.9 Discussion.....	23
2.10 Conclusion.....	25
Chapter 3 Materials and Methods.....	27
3.1 Experimental	27
3.2 Experimental procedures and characterization data.....	31
Chapter 4 REFERENCES.....	53

Chapter 5 LC-MS ANALYSIS DATA56

Appendix

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. <i>N</i> -glycan diversification and destination.....	2
Figure 2. Elements that cause the massive diversity of complex type <i>N</i> -glycans.....	3
Figure 3. General strategies of chemo-enzymatic synthesis.....	4
Figure 4. Brief illustration of the AGCS strategy.	6
Figure 5. A representative demonstration of <i>N</i> -glycan synthesis with AGCS strategy.	7
Figure 6 The Basic combination of complex type <i>N</i> -glycans.....	9
Figure 7 Retrosynthetic analysis of AGC 1	10
Figure 8 Further disconnection of building blocks.....	11

LIST of SCHEMES

Scheme 1 Synthesis of Glucosaminyl Building Blocks.....	12
Scheme 2 Synthesis of the Mannosyl Building Block.....	13
Scheme 3 Synthesis of the Galactosyl Building Block.....	13
Scheme 4 Synthesis of the Glucosyl Building Block.....	14
Scheme 5 Synthesis of disaccharide without galactoside	14
Scheme 6 Synthesis of disaccharide 5 from acceptor 7	15
Scheme 7 Alternative pathway to the lactosyl donor.....	16
Scheme 8 Synthesis of tetrasaccharide 2	16
Scheme 9 Synthesis of Core Trisaccharide acceptor 4	17
Scheme 10 Installation of tetrasaccharide part and benzylidene removal.	19
Scheme 11 Conversion of disaccharide to donor 30	20
Scheme 12 Completion of whole structure and global deprotection.	21

LIST of Charts

Chart 1 LC-MS spectra of the products from enzymatic fucosylations.....	22
Chart 2 LC-MS spectra of the products from enzymatic sialylation.....	23
Chart 3 LC and MS-MS of AGC 1.....	56
Chart 4 LC of enzymatic fucosylations.....	57
Chart 5 MS-MS Spectra of enzymatic fucosylations.....	58
Chart 6 Comparison of MS3 between FUT1 and FUT6 product.....	60
Chart 7 LC of enzymatic sialylations.....	60
Chart 8 MS-MS spectra of enzymatic sialylations.....	61
Chart 9 Comparison of MS3 between ST3Gal and ST6Gal product.....	62

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full Name
Ac	Acetyl
ACN	Acetonitrile
Ar	Aryl
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
β 3GlcNAcT	β 3- <i>N</i> -acetylglucosaminyltransferase
Bn	Benzyl
brsm	Based on recovered starting materials
Bz	Benzoyl
Bu	Butyl
CAN	Ammonium cerium(IV) nitrate
CMK	Cytidine monophosphate kinase
CMP	Cytidine 5'-monophosphate
COSY	Correlated spectroscopy
Cp_2HfCl_2	Di(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride
CSA	Camphorsulfonic acid
CSS	CMP-sialic acid synthetase

CTP	Cytidine triphosphate
DAST	Diethylaminosulfur trifluoride
DBU	1,8-Diazabicyclo(5.4.0)undec-7-ene
DCM	Dichloromethane
DDQ	2,3-Dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone
DMAP	4-(Dimethylamino)pyridine
DMF	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide
EA	Ethyl acetate
<i>E. coli.</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
EDCI	1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide)
FUT	Fucosyltransferase
Gal	Galactose
GDP	Guanine Diphosphate
GlcNAc	<i>N</i> -Acetylglucosamine
h	Hour
HMBC	Heteronuclear Multiple Bond Correlation
HSQC	Heteronuclear single quantum coherence spectroscopy
Hz	Hertz
IPTG	Isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside

<i>J</i>	Coupling constant
LacNAc	<i>N</i> -Acetyllactosamine
Lev	Levulinoyl
Man	Mannose
MHz	Megahertz
μL	Microliter
μM	Micromolar
μm	Micrometer
μmol	Micromole
mL	Milliliter
mM	Micromolar
mmol	Millimole
MS	Mass spectrometry
MS-MS	Tandem mass spectrometry,
<i>m/z</i>	mass-to-charge ratio
Neu5Ac	<i>N</i> -Acetylneuraminic acid
NIS	<i>N</i> -Iodosuccinimide
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
NPhth	Phthalimide

OD 600	Optical density of a sample measured at a wavelength of 600 nm
PEP	Phosphoenolpyruvate
Per-AcGal	β -D-Galactose pentaacetate
Per-AcGlc	β -D-Glucose pentaacetate
Ph	Phenyl
Pk	Pyruvate kinase
PMB	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzyl
PMP	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl
PPA	Pyrophosphatase
PTSA	<i>p</i> -Toluenesulfonic acid
Pyr	Pyridine
rt	Room temperature
ST3Gal	β -galactoside α -2,3-sialyltransferase
ST6Gal	β -galactoside α -2,6-sialyltransferase
STol	<i>p</i> -toluenethiol
TB medium	Terrific Broth Medium
TES	Triethylsilane
Tf ₂ O	Trifluoromethanesulfonic anhydride

TfOH	Trifluoromethanesulfonic acid
TFA	Trifluoroacetic acid
TLC	Thin layer chromatography
TMS	Trimethylsilyl
TMSOTf	Trimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate
UDP	Uridine 5'-diphosphate

Chapter 1 Introduction

N-glycans are oligosaccharides covalently attached to proteins at the asparagine (Asn) residue by *N*-glycosidic bond. The reaction is catalyzed by oligosaccharyl transferase for the transfer of an oligosaccharide from dolichol pyrophosphoryl polysaccharide to the Asn side-chain amide nitrogen, followed by trimming of terminal sugars processed by glycosidases in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and further diversified with the aid of glycosyltransferases in the Golgi apparatus to form various glycoforms with distinct compositions and properties (**Figure 1**).¹ They are essential in numerous intercellular recognition events, including the innate immune signaling through interaction with different lectins on immune cells and in circulations, and the binding of specific *N*-glycoforms to receptors that affect cellular functions.¹ Moreover, *N*-glycans contribute directly to disease progressions such as cancer metastasis, inflammation, and viral and bacterial infections.¹

Figure 1. *N*-glycan diversification and destination.

The bold arrows show the possible elongation. The pentasaccharide in the golden box is the basic component of *N*-glycans.

Complex type *N*-glycans is one of three major classes of *N*-glycans, which usually exist as mixtures in glycoforms, are highly diversified and “asymmetric” (**Figure 2**), and are difficult to identify under current sequencing methods.² The diversity is resulted from the lack of template and various possible glycosylations with different glycosyltransferases, such as fucosyltransferases and sialyltransferases involved in the bio-synthesis, while the asymmetry results from the combination of mixed substrates and distinct regio-isomers (**Figure 2**). It is estimated that more than 20,000 structures of *N*-

glycans are present in human glycome, representing a major challenge in obtaining pure glycans and homogeneous glycoproteins to study the effect of *N*-glycans on protein folding, structure and function.³

Figure 2. Elements that cause the massive diversity of complex type *N*-glycans.

(A) There are 5 possible attaching sites for GlcNAc. (B) For each GlcNAc attached, there are two possible sites for galactosylation to yield the type I- or type II-LacNAc moiety. (C) The LacNAc moieties can be extended from the existing ones to form regio-isomers which have the same mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) as other regio-isomers. (D) For each LacNAc moiety, two types of α fucosylation could take place. When it is attached to the non-reducing end followed by α sialylation, six variants will be generated. (E) In addition, every compound may have another modification through core fucosylation.

Thus, the precise functional differences among complex type *N*-glycans have not yet been well elucidated, especially in cases of regio-isomers which are lack of homogeneous standards for the study³. Approaches to obtain various homogeneous samples in the past decades mainly relied on chemical synthesis, but the complexity of protecting

manipulation complicated the works and made the synthetic process very tedious. Later on, methods based on combined chemical and enzymatic reactions have made some improvement in the preparation of pure *N*-glycans for the study of their roles in glycoproteins⁴. Recently, further advances in chemo-enzymatic methods using the existing or engineered enzymes to introduce the fucose and sialic acid residues, which contribute to the major diversity of *N*-glycans, to the *N*-glycan terminals have been developed.⁵ This chemo-enzymatic approach can be divided to two major strategies: the “convergent strategy” and the “divergent strategy” (Figure 3).^{6,7}

Figure 3. General strategies of chemo-enzymatic synthesis.

(A) The convergent strategy, namely modular synthesis: constructing the diversified antennae and converting them to proper donors which could be installed onto the core acceptor. After global deprotection the target compound is obtained. (B). The divergent strategy: installing a proper protected sugar or non-enzymatic reactive sugar (noted M) onto the orthogonally protected core at a specific site, followed by global deprotection and extension of the structure by enzymatic glycosylation to yield the target compounds.

Although these methods have partially solved the issue of complexity and through which various forms of asymmetric antennae have been prepared, the most critical issue in the chemo-enzymatic synthesis is to design suitable common intermediates without protecting group to control the enzymatic glycosylation and make a good use of precious enzyme. Because, on one hand, the introduction of protecting group or the masking sugar in the divergent chemo-enzymatic strategy is relatively expensive, and on the other hand, the process may also be costly as it often requires excess of enzymes in early stages and may have the problem of protecting group migration in the water phase to affect the selectivity of the enzymatic glycosylation. Hence, access to such common intermediates which can be prepared efficiently with short steps and served as substrates for selective enzymatic glycosylation is highly desirable as this approach will require less enzymes and eliminate many orthogonal protections and deprotection steps that often result in low-yield reactions.

It is known that the upregulation or downregulation of sialylation and fucosylation may occur in some cancers.¹ There may be same phenomena among the occurrence of some specific regio-isomers of *N*-glycan complex type bearing fucosylation and sialylation. To distinguish the normal and abnormal glycoforms, we need standard. Yet we do not just desire making standards, we also want to make good use the synthetic compound. That is to say, to test the specific regio-isomers' substrate specificity of glycosyltransferases, which could also help us study glycoforms. Because that if we know some regio-isomers are not good substrate of some glycosyltransferase, we may see some glycosylated regio-isomers as "abnormal", which may relate to diseases. With this motivation, we designed an alternative strategy based on a convergent approach, called Asymmetric Glycan as Common-substrate Strategy (AGCS), that involves controlling the

enzymatic extension by preinstalling the *N*-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) residue at a specific chain to serve as an acceptor substrate for glycosyltransferases, such as α -fucosyltransferase 1 (FUT1, **Figure 4**), β -galactoside α -2,3-sialyltransferase (ST3GAL) and β -galactoside α -2,6-sialyltransferase (ST6GAL). The unique feature of the strategy is to use a simple convergent chemical synthesis to build up an asymmetric framework that could be derived to asymmetric targets by enzymatic glycosylation with increasing diversity in a regio-selective manner. Therefore, this strategy will create an intermediate that can not only be diversified to a variety of asymmetric glycans without further protecting/masking steps which are often needed in divergent strategy, but also eliminate the underlying obstacles in differentiating the stages of convergent strategy (**Figure 3**). This approach also provides an alternative opportunity to facilitate our understanding of the specificity of glycosyltransferases in *N*-glycan synthesis, that is to say, this AGC should be similar with the immature structure being diversified from common core structure of *N*-glycans, on which we may test the activities of glycosyltransferases in a more natural substrate,¹ which is not be done in the modular synthesis. In addition, the products generated from the common substrates can be explored as substrates for the synthesis of homogeneous glycoforms to study the effect of glycosylation on the structure and function of glycoproteins.⁸ Moreover, the fragile fucosylated isomers could be used as standards for the development of new methods for glycan sequencing.

Figure 4. Brief illustration of the AGCS strategy.

Using the commercial starting material to build up an asymmetric structure to restrict the enzymatic glycosylation site so the specific asymmetric complex type *N*-glycan can be acquired.

This strategy is demonstrated below, starting from the synthesis of **AGC 1** (**Figure 4**) for the selective enzymatic glycosylation to give five complex type glycans. Though there are 3 regio-isomers of **AGC 1** by galactosylation. The first thing we have to check the route planned is feasible or not. Hence, we only chose arbitrarily one compound as our chemical synthesis target. The reducing end of the chosen target **AGC 1** was attached with a five-carbon linker (C5 linker, C₅H₅NH₂) with terminal amine which can be used for the preparation of glycan arrays to study protein-glycan interactions, to allow a high-throughput exploration of the specificities of a diverse range of glycan-binding proteins.⁹ Through this process, we may identify individual *N*-glycans which are involved in different biological functions.

Figure 5. A representative demonstration of *N*-glycan synthesis with AGCS strategy.

(a) FUT1, GDP-fucose. (b) FUT6, GDP-fucose. (c) FUT8, GDP-fucose. (d) ST3Gal, CMP-Neu5Ac. (e) ST6Gal, CMP-Neu5Ac.

Chapter 2 Results and Discussion

2.1 Retrosynthetic Analysis.

When examining the structures (**Figure 4**) of the asymmetric complex type *N*-glycans, we can see that one of the basic variations of complex type *N*-glycans is the LacNAc or GlcNAc glycosylation patterns; that is to say, the combination of numbers and the linked positions, such as the red marked oxygen on the mannose residue or the LacNAc(s). Hence, the key of obtaining samples of desired structure is to introduce the LacNAc(s) onto certain site(s) in the synthesis.

Hence, in our strategic design, we tried to use selective ring opening of the benzylidene protecting group on the mannose to control the linking position of LacNAc (**Figure 4**), which is perhaps the simplest way to prepare the key intermediate. Because there are only four positions on the two mannose residues (red marked) to be linked with LacNAc, which are the 2'/4' oxygens on the β -1,3 mannoside arm and the 2'/6' oxygens on the β -1,6 mannoside arm. If we incorporate an orthogonal protecting group for the 2' oxygen of mannoside with the benzylidene protecting group to differentiate the 4'/6' oxygen under selective ring opening reaction, we may achieve the basic variation in the convergent synthesis by exposing the desired glycosylation site accordingly.

Figure 6 The Basic combination of complex type *N*-glycans.

(A). **AGC 1** is one of a set of regio-isomers with different numbers of GlcNAc or LacNAc that linked to the core branch mannose or the galactose. (B). By using selective ring-opening and protection, all the necessary combinations could be achieved.

Therefore, we divide the whole structure into three parts, including the core trisaccharide **4**, the LacNAc bearing tetrasaccharide **2** for later enzymatic extension and the disaccharide **3** without galactose (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7 Retrosynthetic analysis of **AGC 1**

Ac: Acetyl, Bn: benzyl, Ph: phenyl, PMP: *p*-methoxyphenyl, NPhth: phthalimide.

The core trisaccharide **4** is the common acceptor structure of all kinds of *N*-glycans and is composed of the β -1,4 linked mannosyl chitobiose moiety, while the mannosyl parts of the tetrasaccharide **2** and disaccharide **3** are the donor glycosyl components for the assembly of asymmetric *N*-glycans (**Figure 1**).

According to the retrosynthetic analysis, we prepared these building blocks as fully protected forms for chemical synthesis. From this we disconnected compound **2** to yield the combination of disaccharide **3** and LacNAc building block **5** (**Figure 8**), which could be generated from the galactosyl donor **6**, and the acceptor **7**. Finally, the disaccharide **3** can be disconnected to the glucosaminyl building block **8** and mannoside **9**. In the

meantime, the protected core could be acquired from assembly of a glucoside and chitobiose based on a reported method^{4a}. In this design the combination of mannoside **9** and the glucosaminyl donor **8** can lead to a variety of branch forms (**Figure 6**), without complicated protecting groups manipulation.

Figure 8 Further disconnection of building blocks.

STol: *p*-toluenethiol. The red line shows structure disconnection.

2.2 Synthesis of the Monosaccharide Building Blocks.

Scheme 1 Synthesis of Glucosaminy Building Blocks.

(a) Phthalic anhydride, NaOMe, triethylamine. (b) Ac₂O, Pyr, 76%, over 2 steps. (c) BnNH₂, THF. (d) Cl₃CCN, DBU, DCM, 42%, over 2 steps. (e) *p*-toluenethiol, BF₃·Et₂O, DCM, 74%. (f) NaOMe, MeOH. (g) Benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal, ACN, 72%, over 2 steps. (h) Ac₂O, Pyr, 99%. (i) TES, TFA, DCM, 0 °C, 88%. (j) BnBr, NaH, DMF, 90%. (k) TES, TFA, DCM, 0 °C, 84%. (l) N₃(CH₂)₅OH, NIS, TfOH, -40 °C, 70%.

Pyr: pyridine. THF: tetrahydrofuran. DBU: 1,8-Diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene. DCM: dichloromethane. ACN: acetonitrile. TES: triethylsilane. TFA: trifluoroacetic acid. NIS: *N*-Iodosuccinimide. TfOH: triflic acid. STol: *p*-methylphenylthio.

In the beginning, we prepared the glucosaminy building block and the mannoside in multi-gram scale. The glucosaminy building blocks was generated from commercially available d-(+)-glucosamine hydrochloride (GlcNH₂-HCl) in routine steps (Scheme 1), while the mannosyl building blocks were generated from commercially available mannose (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2 Synthesis of the Mannosyl Building Block.

(a) Ac_2O , I_2 . (b) *p*-methoxy phenol, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$, DCM, 70% over 2 steps. (c) NaOMe, MeOH. (d) Benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal, ACN, 75%, over 2 steps. (e) Bu_2SnO , MeOH, reflux. (f) BnBr, CsF, DMF, 95 °C, 86%, over 2 steps. DMF: Dimethylformamide. PMP: *p*-methoxy phenyl.

Scheme 3 Synthesis of the Galactosyl Building Block.

(a) BnNH_2 , THF, 90%. (b) Cl_3CCN , DBU, DCM, 72%.

For the rest part, the galactosyl building block was generated by protecting group manipulations with the commercially available β -D-galactose pentaacetate (**Per-Ac-Gal**) (**Scheme 3**). For the mannoside linked to the chitobioside structure, we decided to use the glucoside building block **20** (**Scheme 4**) as a “masked” mannose to avoid the troublesome β -mannosylation reaction. Hence, from the commercially available β -D-glucose pentaacetate (**Per-Ac-Glc**) we prepared the glucose building block which could be converted to mannoside by inverting its 2' oxygen after installation onto the chitobioside structure (**Scheme 4**).

Scheme 4 Synthesis of the Glucosyl Building Block.

(a) *p*-toluenethiol, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$, DCM, 75%. (b) NaOMe, MeOH. (c) Benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal, ACN, 70%, over 2 steps. (d) Bu_2SnO , MeOH, reflux. (e) *p*-methoxybenzyl chloride, CsF, DMF, 95 °C, 80%, over 2 steps, brsm. (f) Levulinic acid, EDCI, DMAP, DCM, 60%.

brsm: based on recovered starting material. PMB: *p*-methoxy benzyl. Lev: levulinoyl.

2.3 Synthesis of the Disaccharide without Galactose.

Because disaccharide **3** is a partial structure of **2**, so we decide to synthesize the disaccharide **3** first (Scheme 5). Upon treatment of compounds **8** and **9** with trace trimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate (TMSOTf), the disaccharide **3** was formed. However, the yield is not ideal, perhaps the benzylidene structure is labile in the imidate glycosylation condition that interferes with the reaction.

Scheme 5 Synthesis of disaccharide without galactoside

(a) TMSOTf, DCM, -50 °C, 58%.

TMSOTf: Trimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate.

2.4 Synthesis of the Galactose bearing Tetrasaccharide.

Scheme 6 Synthesis of disaccharide **5** from acceptor **7**.

(a) TMSOTf, DCM, -40 °C, 2.5h, **5**: 36%, **24**: 49%.

To complete the synthesis of the tetrasaccharide, we have to build up the lactosyl donor **5** first. The disaccharide **5** here has the same role as a “mask”, similar to those acetylated saccharide units in the divergent synthesis (**Figure 3**). After sialylation, the sialyl product restricts the access of fucosyltransferase resulting in a site selective fucosylation,⁶ just like the role acetyl protecting group plays in the chemo-enzymatic synthesis. Nevertheless, in the synthesis of donor **5** a byproduct orthoester **24** was formed (**Scheme 6**). After many trials the reaction was not improved, even under the milder conditions (reduced amount of TMSOTf, lowered reaction temperature), the byproduct **24** was still formed. This situation was finally overcome by the use of diol compound **25** as acceptor (**Scheme 7**),¹¹ and in this reaction, no orthoester was formed, and after acetylation, the disaccharide donor **5** was obtained. After selective ring opening of compound **3**, followed by glycosylation with the thioglycoside of disaccharide **5** in the presence of NIS and TfOH, the tetrasaccharide **2** was formed (**Scheme 8**).

Scheme 7 Alternative pathway to the lactosyl donor

(a) TES, TFA, DCM, 0 °C, 85%. (b) **9**, TMSOTf, DCM, -65 °C, 2h, 40%.
(c) Ac₂O, Pyr, 2h, 99%

Scheme 8 Synthesis of tetrasaccharide **2**

(a) TES, TfOH, -78 °C, 50%. (b) NIS, TfOH, **5**, DCM, -50 °C, 92%

2.5 Synthesis of the core trisaccharide.

Scheme 9 Synthesis of Core Trisaccharide acceptor **4**

(a) NIS, TfOH, $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 71%. (b) TES, TFA, $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 68%. (c) **20**, NIS, TfOH, $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 78%
(d) hydrazine acetate, DCM, sonicate, 94%. (e) Tf_2O , Pyr. (f) Tetrabutyl ammonium acetate, toluene, sonicate, 95%, over 2 steps. (g) DDQ, H_2O , DCM, 75%, brsm.
DDQ: 2,3-Dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone.

The core trisaccharide acceptor structure was built up by the combination of glucosamine building blocks acceptor **14** and donor **16** followed by attachment of building block **20** (Scheme 9). After deprotection of the levulinoyl group and inversion of the 2' oxygen, the acceptor **4** was acquired.

2.6 Installation of the tetrasaccharide on core.

After deprotection of *p*-methoxy phenyl (PMP) group at the reducing end of compound **2**, and conversion to a fluoride donor (62% over 2 steps), the glycosylation of core trisaccharide acceptor **4** went smoothly under promotion of silver triflate (AgOTf) and

di(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride (Cp_2HfCl_2) in toluene to yield the heptasaccharide **29** in 60%, followed by removal of the benzylidene to yield the acceptor **28** in 40% yield (**Scheme 10**).

Scheme 10 Installation of tetrasaccharide part and benzylidene removal.

(a) CAN, ACN, toluene, H₂O. (b) DAST, DCM, -10 °C, 49% over 2 steps.

(c) AgOTf, Cp₂HfCl₂, toluene, -40 °C, 40%. (d) PTSA, ACN, 60%.

CAN: Ceric ammonium nitrate. DAST: Diethylaminosulfur trifluoride.

AgOTf: Silver trifluoromethanesulfonate.

Cp₂HfCl₂: Di(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride.

PTSA: *p*-Toluenesulfonic acid.

2.7 Installation of the disaccharide and global deprotection.

We then used the disaccharide **3** for the synthesis of the rest part of the AGCS, and after removing the PMP group and conversion to an imidate (**Scheme 11**), we found that the imidate with benzylidene is a good donor for the synthesis of the fully protected compound **31** (**Scheme 12**). Finally, the compound **33** underwent global deprotection (detailed in **Chapter 3.2**) to give **AGC 1** in 44% yield (**Scheme 12**).

Scheme 11 Conversion of disaccharide to donor **30**

(a) CAN, ACN, toluene, H₂O, 62%. (b) DBU, CCl₃CN, DCM, 0 °C, 76%.

Scheme 12 Completion of whole structure and global deprotection.

28 + 30

(a) TMSOTf, DCM, -50 °C, 70%. b) global deprotection, 44%.

2.8 Enzymatic Glycosylation.

To test whether the chemo-enzymatic route is feasible, we used the α -1,3/1,2-fucosyltransferases and α -1,6-fucosyltransferases (obtained by methods in **Chapter 3.1**) to proceed fucosylation to generate different region-isomers of fucosylated products (**Chart 1**). Besides, **AGC 1** also was sialylated with α -2,3/2,6-sialyltransferases (see

Chapter 3.1) as planned (**Figure 5**).¹⁰ The reactions were monitored by liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS) (PGC Column, see **Chapter 3**).

According to the mass spectroscopy (MS), we found that the products of fucosylation and sialylation were formed (**Chart 1** and **Chart 2**) accordingly, though incomplete sialylation and fucosylation (FUT1 and FUT8) were observed. The MS2 and MS3 spectra showed different patterns between the starting material and products from fucosyltransferases, and in the glycosylations with sialyltransferases.

Chart 1 LC-MS spectra of the products from enzymatic fucosylations.

A: Product of FUT1. B: Product of FUT6. C: Product of FUT8.

Chart 2 LC-MS spectra of the products from enzymatic sialylation.

A: Product of α -2,3-STGal. B: Product of α -2,6-STGal

2.9 Discussion.

Now we have synthesized an *N*-glycan using the chemical method, which can be used as substrate for further enzymatic structure extension. We have also developed a strategy with common protecting groups to avoid the use of various protecting groups that a divergent strategy is needed. However, many steps gave poor yields among the chemical glycosylations, especially the steps for disaccharides **3** (Scheme 5) and **5** (Scheme 6), due to side product forming reactions. And also, in this approach we took more steps in chemical synthesis than the modular synthesis. If we change the glucosaminyl donor to a more armed donor, like the one with more benzyl protection, the performance may be better, yet needs more protecting group manipulation.

Anyhow, this chemical synthesis showed a way with less protecting groups to furnish a complex type *N*-glycan structure than full chemical synthesis, and indicated the possibility to assemble another 3 regio-isomers, simply by changing the linking sites of the lactosamine moiety. Even though, this planning still got some benefits, for instance, the **ACG 1** could be used as substrate for testing activity of glycosyltransferases to resolve the details of *N*-glycan bio-synthesis, because the structure is more like natural immature *N*-glycan.¹

From the fucosylation results we may see that the **AGC 1** is good substrate for FUT6 however is not for FUT1 and FUT8 which showed uncompleted reaction. If we have other regio-isomers to be compared, we may find out that whether there is preference of fucosyltransferase among them and may find the meaning of those glycoforms. Yet the sialyltransferases used here were not human enzymes, hence the detailed reactivity test that help human glycomic study should be done in the future.

The other application of the **AGC 1** is the making standard for MS sequencing study. We acquired the LC and MS-MS data of **AGC 1** (**Chapter 5: Chart 3**), fucosylated compounds (**Chapter 5: Chart 4, 5, 6**) and sialylated compounds (**Chapter 5: Chart 7, 8, 9**). Nevertheless, the tough synthesis process halted us from acquiring standards contain both fucosylation and sialylation. We only got primary enzymatic glycosylation product. If we have prepared more amount of **AGC 1**, we may proceed the secondary glycosylation by enzymes, and give more answers to distinguishing glycans bearing both sialylation and fucosylation.

As for the further application of secondary enzymatic glycosylation, this strategy can provide a route to sialy-Lewis X (SLe^x), which is an important antigen in many diseases. For another thing, if we treat the products of FUT6 with ST3Gal. By this strategy we can build up a series of compounds bearing SLe^x in different antennae of complex type

glycans, which may help the study of binding specificity of various lectins by glycan array. The other application of compound **AGC 1** is its use as substrate for β 3-*N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase (β 3GlcNAcT), which we may achieve the synthesis of *N*-glycans with poly-LacNAc structure on different antennae, which can be used as glycan sequencing standards or other antigen studies. Also, those secondary enzymatic glycosylated product could be used as substrate to test FUT8 reactivity, from which we may get more standard for studying core fucosylation which is associated with many biological functions.¹

2.10 Conclusion.

In summary, we have developed an efficient chemo-enzymatic route to asymmetric *N*-glycans of complex type, with simplified protecting group manipulation and elimination of differential acetylation and the potential problem of trans-acetylation, and at the same time taking advantage of the specificity of glycosyltransferases toward-protecting group-free substrates in enzymatic synthesis to create diversity. The asymmetric structure is created simply through the selective ring opening of benzylidene on necessary mannose building block and installation of the lactosaminyl building block in the early stage.

This route still faces some trivial problems of protecting group manipulations in chemical synthesis, and may not be the most efficient method for the synthesis of products with higher complexity. Nevertheless, with this improved process, we have better and flexible access to a series of close-related antennae structures (**Figure 5**) for further study. The representative intermediate made by the chemical synthesis of this route is a common substrate for different glycosyltransferases, which give more diverse products in the

subsequent selective enzymatic glycosylation than that generated from the modules produced chemo-enzymatically.

Chapter 3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Experimental

Materials

Materials: All reagents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Across and used without further purification. Anhydrous dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2), *N,N*-dimethyl formamide (DMF), toluene, methanol (MeOH), acetonitrile (CH_3CN) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from a commercial source without further distillation. Pulverized Molecular Sieves MS-4Å (Aldrich) for glycosylation were activated by heating at 350 °C for 3 h. Reactions were monitored by analytical analysis. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) on EM silica gel 60 F254 plates were performed and visualized under UV (254 nm) or stained with acidic ceric ammonium molybdate or p-anisadehyde. Flash chromatography was performed on silica gel (Merck) of 40-63 μm particle size. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE 600 (600 MHz) spectrometer at 25 °C. All ^1H Chemical shifts (in ppm) were assigned according to CDCl_3 ($\delta = 7.24$ ppm) and D_2O ($\delta = 4.80$ ppm). ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained with Bruker AVANCE 600 spectrometer and calibrated with CDCl_3 ($\delta = 77.23$ ppm). Coupling constants (*J*) were reported in hertz (Hz). Splitting patterns are described using the following abbreviations: s, singlet; brs, broad singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; q, quartet; dd, doublet of doublet; m, multiplet. ^1H NMR spectra were reported to include the following information: chemical shift, multiplicity, coupling constant(s), and number(s) of protons. High resolution ESI mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker Daltonics spectrometer.

The synthesis of compound **4**, **9**, **11~18**, **20~23**, **26**, **27** were accomplished by the methods mentioned in reference 4, while the synthesis of compound **5**, **25** was done by the method mentioned in the reference 11.

MALDI-TOF

A 1- μ L reaction mixture was mixed with 1- μ L matrix substance (10 mg/mL 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid in 1% acetonitrile solution containing 0.1% TFA), and applied onto a metal target plate, which was then loaded to Ultraflex II TOF/TOF 200 (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) for detection in a mass range of 500-4000 Da in a linear-positive mode. The results were analyzed by FlexAnalysis (Bruker Daltonics) to measure the ratios of substrates and reaction products.

LC-MS-MS

N-glycans modified by glycosyltransferases were analyzed by LC-ESI-MS on a LTQ Orbitrap XL ETD mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, San Jose, CA) equipped with Waters Acquity UPLC (Waters, Milford, MA), using a PGC HT column (1.0 mm x 150 mm, 3 μ m, Thermo Fisher) with homemade heating oven at 190 °C. Briefly, the gradient employed was 98% buffer A/2% buffer B at 2 min to 40% buffer A/60% buffer B at 20 min, with a flow rate of 250 μ L/min, whereas buffer A was 0.1% formic acid/H₂O and buffer B was 0.1% formic acid/80% acetonitrile. Conditions used for full-scan MS analysis: mass range *m/z* 500-2000, resolution 30,000 at *m/z* 400. The most intense ions were sequentially isolated for CID (NCE 35). Electrospray voltage was maintained at 4.0 kV, and the capillary temperature was set at 275 °C. Fragment ions in MS₂ spectra were annotated by Glycoworkbench 2 software for differentiating glycan isomers.

Procedure for enzymatic experiment

The cDNAs encoding the luminal catalytic domains of human FUT1, 6 and 8 were PCR amplified by the following primer pairs: FUT1 5'-CTGTCTCCGGGTAAAGAATTCCATATCCATCAAGACAGCTTT-3' and 5'-

ACTTCTAAAATGTATTTAGAATTCTCAAGGCTTAGCCAATGTCCA-3'; FUT6 5'-
CTGTCTCCGGGTAAAGAATTCCGTGTGTCTCAAGACGATCC-3' and 5'-
ACTTCTAAAATGTATTTAGAATTCTCAGGTGAACCAAGCCGCTAT-3'; FUT8 5'-
CTGTCTCCGGGTAAAGGATCCGATAATGACCATCCTGATCACTCT-3' and 5'-
TCTAAAATGTATTTAGAATTCTTATTTCTCAGCCTCAGGATATG-3'.

The PCR fragments were subcloned into BamHI and EcoRI-cut pcDNA3-hIgG1-Fc vector (a kind gift from Professor S.-L. Hsieh, GRC, Academia Sinica) via Quick-Fusion Cloning kit (Biotool). Fc-tagged FUT1, FUT6, and FUT8 were overexpressed with Expi293 or ExpiCHO expression system (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Transfected cells were lysed with lysis buffer [100 mM sodium phosphate (pH 7.2), 150 mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1X EDTA-free protease inhibitor cock-tail (Roche)] at 4 °C for 20 min and the cell lysates were collected after centrifugation at 15,000 x g for 15 min. Cell lysates were mixed together with the culture supernatants of transfected cells and subjected to purification by protein A affinity chromatography (ÄKTA start protein purification system, GE Healthcare Life Sciences). The purity of the Fc-FUTs were analyzed by gel electrophoresis and stained with Imperial Protein Stain (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

The ST3Gal used was JT16AD from *E. coli*. The JT16AD gene was obtained via PCR from genomic DNA or the cDNA library using a primer 5'-GATATACCATGGAAATGAACAACGACAACACTCTACC-3', and PCR products were ligated into the modified vector pET47b or pET28a with N- or C-terminal His-tag for further affinity purification. To increase the gene expression level, the sialyltransferase was synthesized by codon optimization in *E. coli*. The plasmid with a correct sequence was transformed into ArcticExpress/RIL competent cells by a chemical transformation method. Single colonies were picked and inoculated in a TB medium with kanamycin antibiotics overnight, the cell culture was refreshed with TB medium, and the target

protein expression was induced by IPTG (0.1 mM) until OD 600 reached 0.5. After that, the culture was grown at 16 °C for 24 h. The *E. coli* cells were harvested and disrupted in a buffer containing 50 mM sodium phosphate, pH 8.0, 300 mM sodium chloride, and 10 mM imidazole by a microfluidizer. The cells were centrifuged at 10 000 rpm for 30 min at 4 °C. Then, the supernatant was mixed with Ni-NTA agarose. The bound protein was eluted in the same buffer containing a higher concentration of imidazole (250 mM). The protein concentration was determined by Qubit Protein Quantitation kit (Invitrogen, CA, USA), and the purity was confirmed by SDS-PAGE.^{10a}

The ST6Gal used was Psp2,6ST. The cloning, expression, purification, and crystallization of the putative mature-form recombinant of α 2,6-sialyltransferase produced by *Photobacterium* sp. have previously been reported (Okino et al. 2007).^{10b}

Fucosylation and sialylation

The fucosylation of target *N*-glycans was performed with fucosyltransferase (FUT)1 for terminal α -1,2-, FUT6 for terminal α -1,3-, and FUT8 for core α -1,6-fucosylation. The condition used for the enzymatic reaction was as follows: 100 μ M *N*-glycan acceptor substrate, 1 mM guanosine 5'-diphospho-b-L-fucose (GDP-fucose) and FUT (Fc-FUT1, 2 μ g; Fc-FUT6, 1.5 μ g; Fc-FUT8, 2 μ g) in 20 μ L of reaction buffer (25 mM MOPS, 20 mM MgCl₂, pH 6.5) were mixed and incubated at 37 °C for overnight. The efficiency of fucosylation was monitored by MALDI-TOF MS analysis. Further addition of 100 μ M GDP-fucose and FUTs followed by 37 °C overnight incubation was performed once or twice to ensure complete fucosylation. Final products were analyzed by LC-MS to obtain MS/MS spectra to confirm the *N*-glycan structures. For further NMR scanning, the product was initially purified by C4 cartridge[®] and Envi-Carb SPE cartridge[®], followed by lyophilization and P2-gel purification.

The sialylation reaction was carried out by mixing 55 mmol of N-acetylneuraminic acid (Neu5Ac), 5 mmol of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), 5 mmol of cytidine triphosphate (CTP), 120 mmol of phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) with 50 mM MgCl₂ in 25 mM TrisHCl buffer (pH 8.0) followed by 2000 μmol of cytidine monophosphate kinase (CMK), 1000 μmol of CMP-sialic acid synthetase (CSS), 4000 μmol of Pyruvate kinase (PK), 2000 μmol of pyrophosphatase (PPA), and 2000 μmol of α-2,3-sialyltransferase (JT-FAJ-16) or α-2,6-sialyltransferase (Psp2,6ST) to make up a solution of **AGC 1** (12.5 mM). The progress was monitored by TLC. After the completion of the reaction (21 hours), the proteins in the reaction mixture were removed by holding the temperature at 90 °C for 30 min, followed by centrifugation (5000 rpm, 20 min) and filtration with a 0.22 μm filter. The filtrate was then purified by C-18 gel chromatography and eluted by a gradient from 100% H₂O to 10% methanol in H₂O.^{10a}

3.2 Experimental procedures and characterization data

To a solution of **14** (1.25 g, 2.62 mmol) in THF (10 mL) was added benzylamine (0.35 mL). The mixture was stirred overnight until TLC (10% acetone in dichloromethane) indicated formation of product with complete consumption of starting material. The mixture was concentrated in vacuo. The residue was suspended in ethyl acetate (100 mL) and washed with aqueous NH₄Cl (2 x 50 mL), aqueous sodium bicarbonate (100 mL), dried over sodium sulfate, and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (5% acetone in dichloromethane) to afford **32** (0.996 g, 87%) as white crystal. TLC (10% acetone in dichloromethane, v/v): $R_f = 0.29$; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.85-7.83 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.73-7.72 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 5.85 (dd, 1H, $J = 10.7$ Hz,

$J = 8.8$ Hz), 5.62 (t, 1H, $J = 7.9$ Hz), 5.16 (dd, 1H, $J = 10$ Hz, $J = 9.19$ Hz), 4.30-4.24 (m, 2H), 4.18 (dd, 1H, $J = 12.3$ Hz, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 3.93-3.90 (m, 1H), 3.06 (d, 1H, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 2.11 (s, 3H), 2.02 (s, 3H), 1.85 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 170.96, 170.31, 134.61, 123.91, 92.88, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 72.37, 70.65, 69.12, 62.25, 56.30, 21.01, 20.86, 20.69. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_{10}\text{Na}$: 458.1058, found: 458.1074 ($\text{M} + \text{Na}$) $^+$.

To a solution of **32** (0.43 g, 0.901 mmol) in dichloromethane (3 mL) was added 2,2,2-trichloroacetonitrile (0.7 mL), stirred in ice bath. Then 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU) (0.1 mL) was added dropwise. The reaction was kept in ice bath and stirred for 4 h until full conversion of the starting material (monitored by TLC, 30% acetone in hexanes, with additional 1% triethylamine). The reaction was quenched in ice bath with triethylamine (0.5 mL), concentrated in vacuo, dissolved in dichloromethane (50 mL) then washed by aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x 2) and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (5% → 25% acetone in hexanes, with additional 1% triethylamine) to afford **8** (0.34 g, 65%) as pale yellow powder. TLC (30% acetone in hexanes plus 1% triethylamine, v/v): $R_f = 0.35$. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.85 - 7.82 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.74 - 7.71 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 6.485 (d, 1H, 1-H, $J = 8.7$ Hz), 5.86 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 9.1$ Hz, $J = 10.2$ Hz), 5.19 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 9.3$ Hz, $J = 10.3$ Hz), 4.44 (dd, 1H, 6-H, $J = 9.0$ Hz, $J = 10.3$ Hz), 4.34 (dd, 1H, 6-H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, $J = 4.5$ Hz), 4.12 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 2.1$ Hz, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 4.01 - 3.99 (m, 1H, 6-H), 2.09 (s, 3H, COCH_3), 2.01 (s, 3H, COCH_3), 1.97 (s, 3H, COCH_3). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3):

δ 170.87, 170.23, 169.68, 168.84, 167.58, 138.07, 134.69, 131.43, 129.23, 128.42, 125.50, 124.01, 89.98, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 72.85, 70.72, 68.51, 61.74, 53.72, 31.78, 22.85, 21.65, 20.97, 20.95, 20.81, 20.60, 14.31. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for $C_{22}H_{21}Cl_3N_2O_{10}+H$: 581.0309, found: 581.0309 (M + H)⁺.

To a solution of **11** (10 g, 19.9 mmol) in pyridine (40 mL) under ice bath was added acetic anhydride (20 mL). The reaction was stirred for 2 h with until conversion of the starting material (monitored with TLC, 30% Ethyl acetate, EA in hexanes). The reaction was poured into ice water (80 mL), washed with 2N HCl (30 mL x2), then with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (30 mL x2). The organic layer was dried over magnesium sulfate and concentrated with vacuo. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (10% → 30% ethyl acetate in hexanes) to afford **10** (10.7 g, 99%) as colorless oil. TLC (30% ethyl acetate in hexanes): R_f = 0.44. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.85 (m, 2H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.73 (m, 2H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.42-7.24 (m, 6H, Ar-H), 7.07-7.05 (d, 2H, J = 7.02 Hz, Ar-H), 5.87-5.84 (t, 1H, J = 9.36 Hz), 5.75-5.73 (d, 1H, J = 10.14 Hz), 5.50 (s, 1H, PhCHOO), 4.41-4.39 (dd, 1H, J = 3.09 Hz, J = 10.14 Hz), 4.32-4.29 (t, 1H, J = 10.14 Hz), 3.82-3.71 (m, 2H), 2.30 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.85 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 170.32, 168.00, 138.86, 136.98, 134.57, 134.34, 133.83, 131.32, 129.88, 129.31, 128.38, 126.37, 123.85, 123.73, 103.85, 101.77, 79.11, 77.34, 77.13, 76.92, 70.74, 70.61, 54.44.

To a solution of **10** (5.99 g, 10.98 mmol) and activated molecular sieves MS-4Å (6 g) in dichloromethane (60 mL) was stirred in room temperature for one h, then the mixture was cooled to 0 °C. After that the solution was added triethyl silane (17 mL, 0.11 mole), and after 5 min trifluoroacetic acid (7 mL, 0.11 mole) was added slowly. The reaction was monitored by TLC (40% ethyl acetate in hexanes) and after 3.5 h it was shown a full conversion of starting materials. The solution was filtered by Celite, diluted with dichloromethane (60 mL) and washed with ice aqueous sodium bicarbonate until the pH of water layer was higher than 10, then concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (10% → 40% ethyl acetate in hexanes) to afford **7** (5.29 g, 88%) as white foam. TLC (40% ethyl acetate in hexanes, v/v): $R_f = 0.24$. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.84 - 7.83 (m, 2H, Ar-H of NPhth), , 7.72 - 7.70 (m, 2H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.36 - 7.24 (m, 7H, Ar-H), 7.00 (d, 2H, STol-H, $J = 7.8$ Hz), 5.67 (d, 2H, 1-H, $J = 10.7$ Hz), 5.64 (dd, 1H, 2-H, $J = 8.6$ Hz, $J = 10.2$ Hz), 4.58 (dd, 2H, 6-H, $J = 11.8$ Hz, $J = 22.6$ Hz), 4.25 (t, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.3$ Hz), 3.85 - 3.80 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 3.79 - 3.72 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 2.95 (d, 1H, OH, $J = 4.1$ Hz), 2.27 (s, 3H, Ar- CH_3), 1.88 (s, 3H, COCH_3). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 171.29, 168.07, 167.49, 138.62, 137.94, 134.57, 134.38, 133.75, 131.90, 131.47, 129.86, 128.68, 128.05, 127.96, 127.79, 123.88, 123.79, 83.48, 78.50, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 74.59, 73.97, 71.37, 70.46, 53.87, 21.35, 20.86. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_7\text{SNa}$: 593.1557, found: 593.1554 ($\text{M} + \text{Na}$) $^+$.

To a solution of **β -D-Galactose pentaacetate** (5 g, 12.8 mmol) in THF (50 mL) was add benzyl amine (4 mL, 36.6 mmol), and the mixture was stirred for overnight. The

reaction mixture was then concentrated in vacuo. The residue was suspended in ethyl acetate (100 mL) and washed with aqueous NH_4Cl (2 x 50 mL), then washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (100 mL), dried over Na_2SO_4 , and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (30% \rightarrow 40% acetone in hexanes) then concentrated and dried in vacuo. The product was dissolved in dichloromethane (100 mL) then cooled in ice bath, followed by addition of 2,2,2-trichloroacetonitrile (24 mL). After 5 min, DBU (0.4 mL) was added dropwise. The reaction was kept in ice bath and stirred for 3 h until full conversion of the starting material (monitored by TLC, 40% acetone in hexanes, with additional 1% triethylamine). The reaction was quenched in ice bath with triethylamine (0.5 mL), concentrated in vacuo, dissolved in dichloromethane (150 mL) then washed by aqueous sodium bicarbonate (30 mL x 2) and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (19% \rightarrow 20% ethyl acetate in hexanes, with additional 1% triethylamine) to afford **6** (4.29 g, 65% over two steps) as pale yellow solid. TLC (30% acetone in hexanes plus 1% triethylamine, v/v): $R_f = 0.34$. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.64 (s, 1H, CNH), 6.55 (d, 1H, 1-H, $J = 3.6$ Hz), 5.51 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 3.1$ Hz), 5.37 (dd, 1H 6-H, $J = 10.89$, $J = 3.6$ Hz), 5.31 (dd, 2H, 6-H, $J = 10.9$ Hz, $J = 3.6$ Hz), 4.39 (t, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 7.1$ Hz), 4.12 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 11.3$ Hz, $J = 6.6$ Hz), 4.04 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 11.3$ Hz, $J = 6.3$ Hz), 2.12 (s, 3H, COCH_3), 1.98(s, 3H, COCH_3), 1.97(s, 3H, COCH_3), 1.97(s, 3H, COCH_3). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 170.47, 170.28, 170.25, 170.15, 161.05, 93.64, 90.89, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 69.12, 67.64, 67.50, 67.03, 61.40, 20.81, 20.78, 20.75, 20.69. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_3\text{NO}_{10}\text{Na}$: 514.0045, found: 514.0048 ($\text{M} + \text{Na}$) $^+$.

To a solution of **26** (from the reference 4a, 7.06 g, 4.58 mmol) in dichloromethane (150 mL) was added hydrazine acetate (0.85g, 9.16 mmol). The reaction was sonicated in a cleaning tank for four h until the full conversion of the starting material (monitored by TLC, 40% ethyl acetate in hexanes, expanded three times). The solution was diluted with 100 mL dichloromethane and washed with water (50 mL x 4), dried with magnesium sulfate, then concentrated with vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (10% → 40% ethyl acetate in hexanes) to afford **33** (6.15 g 4.26 mmol, 94%) as white foam. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.66-7.50 (m, 7H, AR-H), 7.4-4.8 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.23-7.39 (m, 16H, Ar-H), 6.99 (d, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 6.960 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 6.92 (t, $J = 11.1$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 6.88-6.84 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 6.78-6.75 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 5.44 (s, 1H, PhCHOO), 5.26 (d, $J = 12.5$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.92-4.91 (m, 1H), 4.85 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.83 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.78 (d, $J = 12.3$ Hz, 1H), 4.70 (d, $J = 12.3$ Hz, 1H), 4.64 (d, $J = 12.4$ Hz, 1H), 4.59 (d, $J = 12.8$ Hz, 1H), 4.54-4.44 (m, 4H, 6-H), 4.39 (d, $J = 12.9$ Hz, 1H), 4.36 (d, $J = 12.2$ Hz, 1H), 4.22-4.22 (m, 2H), 4.19-4.09 (m, 4H), 3.89-3.85 (m, 1H), 3.77 (s, 3H, CH_3 of PMB), 3.65-3.70 (m, 2H), 3.59-3.45 (m, 5H), 3.40 (dd, $J = 6.2$ & 12.3 Hz, 1H), 3.32-3.31 (m, 1H), 3.29-3.28 (m, 1H), 3.25-3.20 (m, 1H), 3.19-3.15 (m, 1H), 2.90-2.80 (m, 2H, $-\text{CCH}_2\text{N}_3$), 2.09 (s, 3H, $-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_3$), 1.25-1.00 (m, 4H, $-\text{CCH}_2\text{C}-$), 0.99-0.80 (m, 2H, $-\text{CCH}_2\text{C}-$); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 168.71, 168.20, 167.76, 159.57, 138.88, 138.72, 138.61, 138.11, 138.00, 137.58, 134.23, 134.07, 133.88, 132.01, 131.92, 131.67, 130.78, 129.95, 129.29, 129.19, 128.73, 128.48, 128.46, 128.35, 128.24, 128.21, 128.07, 128.00, 127.75, 127.63, 127.58, 127.53, 127.38, 127.12, 126.28, 125.55, 123.91, 123.38, 114.09, 103.65, 101.41, 98.36, 97.21, 81.58, 80.20, 78.88, 78.17, 76.94,

75.87, 75.42, 74.90, 74.85, 74.76, 74.63, 74.50, 73.46, 72.89, 69.09, 68.90, 68.46, 67.59, 66.51, 56.88, 55.97, 55.53, 51.33, 28.91, 28.51, 23.24, 21.71; ESIMS: m/z calcd for $C_{82}H_{83}N_5O_{19}Na$: 1464.5574; found 1464.5594 ($M + Na$)⁺.

A mixed solution of acceptor **9** (0.65 g, 1.167 mmol) and donor **8** (0.902 g, 1.437 mmol) in toluene as azeotrope was vacuumed for 1 h, then dissolved in dichloromethane (18 mL). The activated molecular sieves (3 g) were added to the solution and the mixture was stirred for 1 h, then cooled to -50 °C, followed by addition of TMSOTf (22 μ L, 0.12 mmol). The temperature of the reaction was gradually raised to 0 °C and the reaction was monitored by TLC (30% acetone in hexanes, developed twice). After the full consumption of the starting material, the reaction was quenched by triethylamine (1 mL) then filtered by Celite. The solution was then washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x 2) and dried over magnesium sulfate, and the solvent was removed under vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (5% \rightarrow 25% acetone in hexanes) to afford **3** (597 mg, 0.68 mmol) as white foam. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.94-7.91 (m, 2H), 7.81-7.78 (m, 2H), 7.49-7.45 (m, 4H), 7.39-7.34 (m, 5H), 7.33-7.27 (m, 5H), 7.23-7.18 (m, 5H), 6.80 (m, 2H), 6.73 (m, 2H), 5.97 (dd, $J = 10.2, 1$ H), 5.58 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 5.32 (s, 1H), 5.28 (dd, $J = 9.9$, 1H), 4.83-4.78 (m, 2H), 4.59 (dd, $J = 9.48$, 1H), 4.481- 4.37 (m, 1H), 4.36-4.34 (m, 1H), 4.31- 4.26 (m, 1H), 4.14-4.11 (m, 1H), 4.04 (dd, $J = 10.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.96 (m, 1H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 3.71 (m, 2H), 3.20 (m, 1H), 2.11 (s, 3H), 2.10 (s,

3H), 1.96 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.8, 170.2, 169.5, 163.4, 155.0, 149.5, 138.2, 137.8, 137.4, 134.4, 131.6, 129.0, 128.9, 128.3, 128.2, 128.2, 127.8, 127.7, 127.6, 126.1, 125.3, 123.6, 123.5, 116.9, 114.6, 101.6, 97.0, 96.2, 78.0, 75.5, 73.7, 72.2, 71.9, 70.4, 69.0, 68.2, 64.3, 62.1, 55.6, 54.5, 20.7, 20.6, 20.5. ESI-MS: m/z (M + H) $^+$ calcd for $\text{C}_{47}\text{H}_{49}\text{NO}_{16}$: 883.30; found: 883.11.

To a solution of **3** (590 mg, 0.67 mmol) in dichloromethane (13 mL) was added activated molecular sieves (1.3 g). The solution was stirred in room temperature for 1 h, then cooled to 0 °C, followed by addition of triethylsilane (0.32 mL). After 5 min, trifluoroacetic acid (0.13 mL) was added slowly. The reaction was monitored by TLC (40% ethyl acetate in hexanes), and after 1 h it was shown the full consumption of the starting materials. The solution was filtered by Celite, diluted with dichloromethane (20 mL) and washed with ice aqueous sodium bicarbonate until the pH of the water layer was higher than 10, then the mixture was concentrated under vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (6% \rightarrow 30% acetone in hexanes) to afford **34** (296 mg, mmol, 50%) as white foam. TLC (40% ethyl acetate in hexanes, v/v): R_f = 0.24. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.87-7.55 (m, 6H, Ar-H), 7.41-7.34 (d, 2H, J = 14.64 Hz, Ar-H), 7.33-7.22 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.05-7.03 (d, 2H, J = 6.89 Hz), 6.76-6.75 (d, 2H, J = 9.47 Hz, Ar-H), 6.71-6.70 (d, 2H, J = 9.47 Hz, Ar-H), 5.82-5.79 (dd, 1H, J = 9.47 Hz, J = 10.33 Hz), 5.52-5.51 (d, 1H, J = 8.61 Hz), 5.19-5.16 (t, 1H, J = 9.47 Hz), 5.14 (s, 1H), 4.82-4.80 (d, 1H, J = 11.19 Hz), 4.51-4.50 (d, 1H, J = 11.19 Hz), 4.46-4.43 (dd, 1H, J = 8.61 Hz, J =

10.33 Hz), 4.27-4.18 (m, 3H), 4.07 (s, 2H), 3.89-3.86 (m, 1H), 3.83-3.81 (dd, 1H, $J = 2.58$ Hz, $J = 9.04$ Hz), 3.73 (s, 3H, CH₃ of PMP), 3.72-3.63 (m, 3H), 3.39-3.37 (dd, $J = 3.06$ Hz, $J = 10.71$ Hz), 3.03-3.00 (q, 1H, $J = 3.56$ Hz), 2.51 (s, 1H, OH), 2.02 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.00 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.86 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ESI-MS: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd for C₄₇H₄₉NO₁₆Na: 907.2474; found: 907.2485 (M + Na)⁺.

A mixed solution of acceptor **34** (290 mg, 0.33 mmol) and donor **5** (348 mg, 0.396 mmol) in toluene as azeotrope was reacted and vacuumed for 1 h, then dissolved in dichloromethane. The activated molecular sieve was added in the solution and stirred for 1 h, then cooled to -50 °C, followed by addition of NIS (178.2 mg, 0.792 mmol) then triflic acid (5.3 μ L, 0.06 mmol) slowly. The reaction was monitored by TLC (20% EA in toluene). After full consumption of the starting material, the reaction was quenched by triethylamine (0.5 mL) then filtered by Celite. The solution was added sodium thiosulfate (1 mL) and water (2 mL), stirred till the color of the solution became white. The organic layer was further washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (5 mL x 2) and dried with magnesium sulfate, removed solvent by vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (2% \rightarrow 10% EA in Toluene) to afford **2** (497 mg, 92%) as white foam. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.70 (d, 1H, Ar-H of NPhth, $J = 6.9$ Hz), 7.65 (d, 1H, Ar-H of NPhth, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 7.59 - 7.53 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.37 (t, 3H, Ar-H, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 7.32 -

7.26 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 7.23 - 7.16 (m, 6H, Ar-H), 6.80 (d, 2H, 1-H, $J = 3.0$ Hz), 6.64 (d, 2H, Ring-H, $J = 9.2$ Hz), 6.58 (d, 2H, Ring-H, $J = 9.0$ Hz), 5.72 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 9.1$ Hz, $J = 10.7$ Hz), 5.55 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 9.0$ Hz, $J = 10.7$ Hz), 5.50 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 8.5$ Hz), 5.40 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 5.21 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 3.9$ Hz), 5.11 (t, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.0$ Hz), 5.05 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 3.0$ Hz), 4.93 (dd, 1H, Ring-h, $J = 8.0$ Hz, $J = 10.4$ Hz), 4.75 - 4.72 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 4.60 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 12.1$ Hz), 4.53 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 12.0$ Hz), 4.37 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 4.39 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 8.6$ Hz), 4.33 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 12.2$ Hz), 4.17 (t, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 3.2$ Hz), 4.12 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.7$ Hz, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 4.08 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 4.3$ Hz), 4.05 - 3.97 (m, 9H, Ring-H), 3.92 (t, 1H, $J = 9.8$ Hz), 3.88 (dd, 1H, Ring-h, $J = 8.9$ Hz, $J = 7.1$ Hz), 3.80 - 3.77 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 3.75 - 3.70 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 3.67 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.58 (t, 2H, Ring-H), 3.41 (d, 1H, $J = 8.6$ Hz), 3.29 (d, 1H, $J = 10.4$ Hz), 3.19 (d, 1H, $J = 9.8$ Hz), 3.06 - 3.02 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 2.05 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.01 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.97 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.93 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.91 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.88 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.81 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.79 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 170.72, 170.43, 170.34, 170.24, 170.17, 170.04, 169.53, 168.83, 168.01, 167.77, 154.89, 150.03, 138.86, 138.28, 137.99, 134.20, 134.05, 133.88, 131.70, 131.37, 129.12, 128.69, 128.57, 128.39, 128.36, 128.31, 128.22, 128.18, 128.10, 128.04, 127.97, 127.91, 127.86, 127.84, 127.37, 127.33, 127.24, 127.16, 127.09, 125.39, 123.67, 123.43, 123.33, 117.67, 114.41, 100.36, 98.28, 97.45, 96.60, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 75.20, 74.44, 73.53, 72.21, 72.03, 71.26, 71.10, 71.04, 70.75, 70.41, 69.06, 69.00, 68.76, 66.85, 66.74, 62.17, 60.96, 55.66, 55.65, 55.47, 54.62, 20.81, 20.75, 20.73, 20.65, 20.62, 20.56. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd for C₈₄H₈₈N₂O₃₂Na: 1659.5218; found: 1659.5211 (M + Na)⁺.

To a solution of compound **2** (3.5 g, 2.13 mmol) in a mixture of acetonitrile (16 mL), toluene (8 mL) and water (4 mL) was added cerium ammonium (3.5g, 6.39 mmol) nitrate in 0 °C. The reaction was stirred for 1 h and monitored by TLC (30% acetone in toluene) to ensure the full consumption of starting material. The reaction was then poured into water (30 mL), extracted with ethyl acetate (15 mL x 3). The organic layer was further washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x 3) and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (2% → 16% acetone in toluene) to afford pale yellow foam. The foam was vacuumed for 1 h and dissolved in dichloromethane (30 mL), then cooled to -40 °C. DAST (0.42 mL, 2.60 mmol) was added slowly. The reaction was monitored by TLC (40% ethyl acetate in hexanes). After the full consumption of starting material, the reaction was quenched by aqueous sodium bicarbonate (1 mL). Additional dichloromethane (10 mL) was added and washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x3). The organic layer was concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (8% → 40% ethyl acetate in hexanes) to afford **35** (1.6 g, 1.04 mmol, 49% over two steps) as pale yellow foam. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ7.73 - 7.64 (m, 4H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.61 - 7.55 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.40 - 7.25 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 7.19 - 7.18 (m, 6H, Ar-H), 6.82 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 5.67 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.7 Hz, *J* = 8.9 Hz), 5.54 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 9.1 Hz, *J* = 10.5 Hz), 5.51 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 5.40 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.5 Hz), 5.30 (dd, 1H, 1-H, JHF = 52.53, *J* = 2.7 Hz), 5.22 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 3.5 Hz), 5.11 (t, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.0 Hz), 4.93 (dd, 1H,

Ring-H, $J = 10.4$ Hz, $J = 7.7$ Hz), 4.75 (dd, 1H, 6-H, $J = 10.5$ Hz, $J = 3.5$ Hz), 4.69 (d, 1H, 6-H, $J = 12.3$ Hz), 4.62 (d, 1H, 6-H, $J = 11.9$ Hz), 4.47 (d, 1H, 6-H, $J = 11.9$ Hz), 4.39 - 4.36 (m, 4H, 6-H), 4.16 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 4.12 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.7$ Hz, $J = 8.5$ Hz), 4.06 - 3.96 (m, 8H, Ring-H), 3.92 (t, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.1$ Hz), 3.86 - 3.84 (m, 1H, Ring-H), 3.82 - 3.76 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 3.60 - 3.57 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 3.39 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 11.1$ Hz, $J = 2.7$ Hz), 3.26 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.6$ Hz), 3.16 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 10.1$ Hz), 3.11 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 2.07 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.02 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.98 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.94 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.93 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.88 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.82 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.80 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 177.11, 170.77, 170.57, 170.47, 170.37, 170.31, 170.16, 169.62, 168.94, 168.13, 167.87, 138.65, 138.07, 138.02, 134.33, 133.98, 131.80, 131.47, 129.24, 128.88, 128.83, 128.56, 128.53, 128.42, 128.37, 128.29, 128.26, 128.15, 127.92, 127.87, 127.57, 127.42, 127.40, 127.00, 123.77, 123.67, 123.45, 100.50, 98.45, 97.34, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 76.00, 75.28, 74.58, 74.22, 73.61, 73.21, 72.63, 72.31, 71.20, 71.11, 70.94, 70.87, 70.82, 70.53, 69.17, 68.98, 68.02, 66.95, 66.70, 62.23, 61.06, 55.55, 54.62, 29.77, 20.92, 20.86, 20.85, 20.84, 20.82, 20.76, 20.72, 20.64. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd for C₇₇H₈₁FN₂O₃₀Na: 1555.4756; found: 1555.4750 (M + Na)⁺.

A mixed solution of acceptor **7** (2.09 g, 3.810 mmol) and donor **6** (2.35 g, 4.770 mmol) in toluene as azeotrope was vacuumed for 1 h, then dissolved in dichloromethane (100 mL). The activated molecular sieves (10 g) were added to the solution and the mixture

was stirred for 1 h, then cooled to -40 °C, followed by addition of TMSOTf (70 μL, 0.381 mmol). The temperature of the reaction was gradually raised to 0 °C and the reaction was monitored by TLC (45% acetone in hexanes, developed twice). After the full consumption of the starting material, the reaction was quenched by triethylamine (1 mL) then filtered by Celite. The solution was then washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x 2) and dried over magnesium sulfate, and the solvent was removed under vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (5% → 25% EA in hexanes) to afford **5** (1.2 g, 1.367 mmol, 36%) as white foam and **24** as pale yellow oil (1.663g, 1.894 mmol, 50%). TLC (45% ethyl acetate in hexanes, v/v): R_f = 0.23 (**5**) and 0.24 (**24**) ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) of **5**: δ 7.84-7.82 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.25-7.11 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.40-7.33 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.29-7.27 (d, J = 8.58 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.01-7.00 (d, 2H, J = 7.87 Hz, Ar-H), 5.69-5.66 (dd, 1H, J = 9.19 Hz, J = 9.98 Hz), 5.62-5.60 (d, 1H, J = 10.61 Hz), 5.25-5.24 (d, 1H, J = 3.49 Hz), 5.01-4.98 (dd, 1H, J = 8.24 Hz, J = 10.45 Hz), 4.74-4.72 (d, J = 12.04 Hz), 4.51-4.49 (d, 1H, J = 12.04 Hz, J = 8.24 Hz), 4.25-4.21 (t, 1H, J = 10.77 Hz), 4.03-3.96 (m, 3H), 3.77 (d, 1H, J = 2.53 Hz), 3.65-3.63 (m, 2H), 2.27 (s, 3H, Ar-CH₃), 2.08 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.02 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.94 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.93 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.83 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃) of **5**: δ 170.57, 170.46, 170.33, 170.22, 169.09, 168.00, 167.49, 138.74, 138.13, 134.57, 134.35, 134.05, 131.93, 131.48, 129.85, 128.78, 128.19, 128.14, 127.53, 123.93, 123.75, 100.61, 83.36, 79.12, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 75.45, 73.88, 72.19, 71.21, 70.60, 69.28, 67.77, 66.93, 61.01, 54.20, 21.38, 20.93, 20.86, 20.76. ESI-MS of **5**: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd C₄₄H₄₇NO₁₆S: 878.2688; found: 900.2513 (M + H)⁺. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) of **24**: δ 7.84-7.82, (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.73-7.72 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.36-7.35 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.31-7.30 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.00-6.99 (d, 1H, J = 8.28 Hz, Ar-H), 5.71-5.68 (dd, 1H, J = 8.53 Hz, J = 10.47 Hz), 5.61 (d, 1H, J = 5.04 Hz), 5.60 (s, 1H), 5.44-5.43 (t, 1H, J = 3.10 Hz), 4.87-4.85 (q, 1H, J = 2.79 Hz), 4.60-4.55 (dd, 2H,

$J = 11.85$ Hz, $J = 16.56$ Hz), 4.37-4.36 (dd, 1H, $J = 4.66$ Hz, $J = 6.27$ Hz), 4.28-4.25 (m, 1H), 4.25-4.22 (t, 1H, $J = 10.39$ Hz), 4.10-4.00 (m, 2H), 3.85-3.81 (m, 2H), 3.77-3.75 (dd, 1H, $J = 4.30$ Hz, $J = 10.93$ Hz), 3.67-3.65 (m, 1H), 2.28 (s, 3H, Ar-CH₃), 2.07 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.02 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.95 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.80 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.59 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃) of **24**: δ 170.64, 170.29, 170.04, 169.96, 167.90, 167.62, 138.76, 138.64, 134.61, 134.36, 134.07, 131.83, 129.81, 128.53, 127.67, 127.60, 127.29, 123.94, 123.70, 123.49, 97.01, 82.77, 79.02, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 76.49, 73.38, 72.75, 72.73, 70.24, 68.65, 66.42, 60.99, 53.87, 36.80, 26.37, 21.39, 20.88, 20.73, 20.63. ESI-MS of **24**: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd for C₄₄H₄₇NO₁₆S: 900.2508; found: 900.2521 (M + Na)⁺.

The mixture of silver triflate (0.415 g, 1.6 mmol) and bis(cyclopentadienyl) hafnium dichloride (0.418 g, 1.1 mmol) was dissolved in toluene (20 mL), and activated molecular sieves were added. The mixture was stirred for 30 min, then cooled to -40 °C. Subsequently the solution of a mixture of donor **35** (0.750 g, 0.49 mmol) and acceptor **4** (1.4 g, 0.63 mmol) in toluene (25 mL) was added dropwise. The reaction temperature was gradually raised to -20 °C and the mixture was stirred for 30 min, quenched with triethylamine (1 mL), and filtered with Celite. The filtrate was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (15 mL x 3) and brine (10 mL), concentrated under vacuo. The residue was purified with flash chromatography (2% → 12% acetone in toluene) to

afford **29** (0.700 g, 0.243 mmol, 40%) as white foam ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.84-7.70 (m, 4H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.66 - 7.62 (m, 8H, Ar-H), 7.55-7.44 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 7.39-7.34 (m, 6H, Ar-H), 7.30-7.24 (m, 8H, Ar-H), 7.24-7.16 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 7.15 - 7.10 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.09-6.96 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 6.96 - 6.91 (m, 7H, Ar-H), 6.91 - 6.76 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 5.56 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.7 Hz, *J* = 9.4 Hz), 5.43 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.8 Hz, *J* = 9.4 Hz), 5.33 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.5 Hz), 5.32 (s, 1H, PhCHOO), 5.21 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 4.3 Hz), 5.17 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.1 Hz), 4.97 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 3.9 Hz), 4.94 - 4.90 (m, 3H, Ring-H and 1-H), 4.88 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 5.2 Hz), 4.86 (s, 1H, 1-H), 4.85 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 12.9 Hz), 4.75 (dd, 2H, Ring-H, *J* = 2.8 Hz, *J* = 9.3 Hz), 4.61 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 12.1 Hz), 4.51 (dd, 2H, Ring-H, *J* = 28.4 Hz, *J* = 12.5 Hz), 4.47 - 4.40 (m, 5H, Ring-H and 1-H), 4.35 (d, 1H, *J* = 12.2 Hz), 4.29 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 12.0 Hz), 4.22 - 4.16 (m, 3H, Ring-H and 1-H), 4.15 - 4.09 (m, 4H, Ring-H), 4.09 - 4.06 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 4.05 - 3.95 (m, 6H, Ring-H), 3.88 - 3.87 (m, 1H, Ring-H), 3.84 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.0 Hz), 3.81 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 3.3 Hz), 3.73 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 11.7 Hz), 3.70 - 3.59 (m, 4H, Ring-H), 3.57 (t, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 7.0 Hz), 3.52 - 3.47 (m, 6H, Ring-H), 3.39 - 3.31 (m, 5H, Ring-H), 3.28 - 3.27 (m, 1H, Ring-H), 3.24 - 3.21 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 3.01 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 9.8 Hz), 2.89 - 2.84 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.84-2.80 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.74 - 2.70 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.07 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.03 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.02 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.92 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.84 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.80 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.80 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.79 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.70 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.31 - 1.23 (m, 4H, CH₂), 1.06 - 1.04 (m, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 170.90, 170.57, 170.49, 170.35, 170.29, 170.16, 169.48, 169.31, 169.03, 168.65, 168.26, 168.15, 167.92, 167.72, 139.33, 138.94, 138.81, 138.69, 138.51, 138.33, 137.95, 137.70, 134.24, 134.06, 134.03, 133.79, 131.90, 131.84, 131.60, 131.51, 130.45, 129.27, 129.23, 128.94, 128.89, 128.78, 128.71, 128.63, 128.47, 128.42, 128.37, 128.29, 128.28, 128.13, 128.09, 128.02, 127.94, 127.85, 127.78, 127.75, 127.44,

127.38, 127.07, 127.00, 126.96, 126.88, 123.83, 123.63, 123.51, 123.34, 102.33, 100.44, 98.54, 98.25, 98.01, 97.37, 97.16, 95.60, 78.86, 77.99, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 76.46, 76.35, 73.53, 73.41, 73.32, 72.96, 72.38, 71.31, 71.24, 71.11, 70.94, 70.58, 70.47, 70.16, 69.69, 69.13, 69.08, 68.64, 68.39, 67.60, 67.01, 66.89, 66.04, 61.22, 61.10, 56.57, 55.91, 55.68, 54.27, 51.27, 28.85, 28.45, 23.18, 20.87, 20.85, 20.78, 20.76, 20.72, 20.70, 20.66. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd for $C_{153}H_{158}N_7O_{49}Na$: 2899.9440; found: 2899.9861 ($M + Na$)⁺.

To a stirring solution of **29** (700 mg, 0.243 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 mL) under 0 °C was added *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (83 mg, 0.48 mmol). The solution was stirred for 4 h and quenched with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (25 mL) and extracted with ethyl acetate (10 mL x 3). The organic layer was further washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL), concentrated under vacuo. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (3% → 15% acetone in toluene) to afford **28** (400 mg, 0.143 mmol, 60%) as white foam. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.85 (d, 1H, Ar-H, *J* = 6.8 Hz), 7.74 - 7.49 (m, 14H, Ar-H), 7.42 - 7.25 (m, 11H, Ar-H), 7.24 - 7.15 (m, 11H, Ar-H), 7.01 - 6.92 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 6.72 - 6.72 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 5.67 (t, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.4 Hz), 5.58 (m, 2H, 1-H and Ring-H), 5.32 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.5 Hz), 5.23 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 2.9 Hz), 5.17 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 5.11 - 5.08 (m, 2H, Ring-H), 4.96 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.0 Hz, *J* = 8.6 Hz), 4.89 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 4.86 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 9.3 Hz), 4.82 (d, 1H,

Ring-H, $J = 11.5$ Hz), 4.79 - 4.76 (m, 1H, Ring-H), 4.65 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 12.4$ Hz), 4.54 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 12.4$ Hz), 4.49 - 4.43 (m, 6H, Ring-H and 1-H), 4.40 (d, 1H, 1-H, $J = 14.2$ Hz), 4.37 - 4.27 (m, 3H, Ring-H), 4.20 - 4.18 (m, 1H, Ring-H), 4.17 - 4.04 (m, 7H, Ring-H), 4.02 - 3.95 (m, 5H, Ring-H), 3.86 (d, 2H, Ring-H, $J = 6.1$ Hz), 3.80 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 9.7$ Hz), 3.65 - 3.61 (m, 3H, Ring-H), 3.53 - 3.45 (m, 5H, Ring-H), 3.38 - 3.20 (m, 6H, Ring-H), 3.01 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 9.4$ Hz), 2.97 (d, 1H, Ring-H, $J = 6.1$ Hz), 2.90 - 2.80 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.08 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.03 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.00 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.98 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.93 (s, 6H, COCH₃), 1.91 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.82 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.23 (m, 5H, CH₂), 1.08 - 1.02 (m, 3H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.04, 170.61, 170.50, 170.41, 170.33, 170.23, 169.69, 169.58, 169.02, 168.16, 167.77, 138.98, 138.82, 138.58, 138.49, 138.18, 138.08, 137.96, 134.54, 134.46, 134.32, 134.16, 133.83, 131.90, 131.75, 131.58, 131.47, 129.81, 128.89, 128.80, 128.65, 128.49, 128.40, 128.38, 128.32, 128.29, 128.03, 128.00, 127.89, 127.77, 127.74, 127.59, 127.52, 127.42, 127.31, 127.17, 127.06, 123.85, 123.74, 123.55, 123.35, 100.53, 98.96, 98.27, 98.05, 97.25, 96.33, 78.97, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 76.17, 75.98, 75.31, 74.72, 74.68, 74.58, 74.50, 73.70, 73.25, 73.02, 72.02, 71.66, 71.24, 71.18, 70.88, 70.73, 70.57, 69.85, 69.29, 69.22, 69.08, 68.37, 67.44, 66.99, 62.39, 62.30, 61.10, 56.63, 55.91, 55.43, 54.84, 51.29, 32.14, 29.92, 29.58, 28.87, 28.47, 27.62, 27.30, 23.20, 22.91, 21.09, 20.94, 20.89, 20.87, 20.78, 20.76, 20.67. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for ESI-MS: m/z calcd C₁₄₆H₁₅₄N₇O₄₉: 2790.9841; found: 2790.9807 (M + H)⁺.

To a solution of compound **3** (465.7 mg, 0.478 mmol) in a mixture of acetonitrile (8 mL), toluene (4 mL) and water (2 mL) was added cerium ammonium nitrate (673.9mg, 1.23 mmol) in 0 °C. The reaction was stirred for 1 h and monitored by TLC (30% acetone in toluene) to ensure the full consumption of starting material. The reaction was then poured into water (30 mL), extracted with ethyl acetate (15 mL x 3). The organic layer was further washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x 3) and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (2% → 16% acetone in toluene) to afford pale yellow oil. The yellow oil (168.4 mg, 0.194 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (3 mL) then cooled in ice bath, followed by addition of 2,2,2-trichloroacetonitrile (0.3 mL). After 5 min, DBU (3 μL) was added dropwise. The reaction was kept in ice bath and stirred for 3 h until full conversion of the starting material (monitored by TLC, 30% acetone in hexanes, with additional 1% triethylamine). The reaction was quenched in ice bath with triethylamine (0.5 mL), concentrated in vacuo, dissolved in dichloromethane (50 mL) then washed by aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10 mL x 2) and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (10% → 40% ethyl acetate in hexanes, with additional 1% triethylamine) to afford **30** as pale yellow foam (228.9 mg, 0.326 mmol, 76.4%). TLC (30% acetone in hexanes plus 1% triethylamine, v/v): $R_f = 0.24$. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.49 (s, 1H, CNH), 7.85-7.85 (m, 2H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.73-7.71 (m, 2H, Ar-H of NPhth), 7.42-7.41 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.34-7.31 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.26-7.21 (m, 4H, Ar-h), 5.95 (s, 1H, PhCHOO), 5.88-

5.85 (t, 1H, $J = 9.56$ Hz, $J = 10.38$ Hz), 5.58-5.57 (d, 1H, $J = 8.38$ Hz), 5.46 (s, 1H), 5.23-5.20 (t, 1H, $J = 9.78$ Hz), 4.73-4.68 (dd, 2H, $J = 12.58$ Hz, $J = 13.55$ Hz), 4.51-4.48 (dd, 1H, $J = 8.38$ Hz, $J = 10.48$ Hz), 4.33-4.31 (dd, 1H, $J = 4.66$ Hz, $J = 12.11$ Hz), 4.24-4.18 (m, 2H), 4.01-3.97 (t, 1H, $J = 9.78$ Hz), 3.91-3.89 (m, 1H), 3.88-3.83 (m, 2H), 3.73-3.69 (m, 1H), 3.19-3.15 (t, 1H, $J = 9.78$ Hz), 2.05 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.03 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.88 (s, 3H, COCH₃). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 170.93, 170.38, 169.68, 160.14, 138.09, 137.41, 134.55, 129.12, 128.51, 128.41, 128.18, 127.92, 126.17, 101.68, 97.10, 95.71, 90.66, 77.76, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 74.00, 73.03, 72.45, 72.27, 70.68, 69.22, 68.29, 66.75, 62.31, 54.64, 20.98, 20.87, 20.73. ESI-MS: m/z calcd for (%). C₄₂H₄₁Cl₃N₂O₁₅: 948.1438; found: 943.1464 (M + Na)⁺²

A mixture of silver triflate (128 mg, 0.16 mmol) and bis(cyclopentadienyl) hafnium dichloride (130 mg, 0.11 mmol) was dissolved in toluene (7 mL), and activated molecular sieves were added. The mixture was stirred for 30 min, then cooled to -40 °C. Subsequently a mixture of donor **30** (150 mg, 0.172 mmol) and acceptor **28** (100 mg, 0.035 mmol) in toluene (8 mL) was added dropwise. The reaction temperature was gradually raised to -20 °C and stirred for 30 min, and the mixture was quenched with triethylamine (1 mL) and filtered with Celite. The filtrate was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate

(5 mL x 3) and brine (3 mL), concentrated under vacuo. The residue was purified with flash chromatography (2% → 12% acetone in toluene) to afford **31** (90 mg, 23.4 μmol, 70%) as white solid. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.34-7.13 (m, 65H, Ar-H), 5.30-5.28 (dd, 2H, *J* = 7.92 Hz, *J* = 9.97 Hz), 5.23-5.22 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.22 Hz), 5.11 (s, 1H), 5.05 (s, 1H), 5.02-5.01 (d, 1H, *J* = 2.35 Hz), 5.00-4.90 (m, 6H), 4.84-4.82 (m, 2H), 4.78-4.68 (m, 5H), 4.64-4.60 (m, 3H), 4.59-4.40 (m, 14H), 4.37-4.30 (m, 4H), 4.28-4.21 (m, 4H), 4.17-4.08 (m, 3H), 4.06-4.00 (m, 4H), 3.96-3.79 (m, 8H), 3.76-3.66 (m, 8H), 3.64-3.60 (m, 5H), 3.58-3.51 (m, 10H), 3.47-3.43 (m, 2H), 3.38-3.28 (m, 6H), 3.23-3.22 (m, 1H), 3.17-3.15 (m, 3H), 3.05-3.03 (m, 1H), 2.15 (s, 3H), 2.09 (s, 3H), 2.00 (s, 3H), 2.00 (s, 3H), 1.98 (s, 3H), 1.97 (s, 3H), 1.94 (s, 3H), 1.87 (s, 3H), 1.78 (s, 3H), 1.76 (s, 3H), 1.64 (s, 3H), 1.63 (s, 3H), 1.53-1.51 (m, 4H), 1.34-1.28 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.89, 171.01, 170.94, 170.86, 170.43, 170.19, 169.95, 169.64, 139.31, 138.92, 138.87, 138.72, 138.57, 138.34, 138.24, 138.14, 129.18, 128.89, 128.81, 128.78, 128.66, 128.61, 128.55, 128.49, 128.39, 128.31, 128.25, 128.21, 128.15, 128.01, 127.94, 127.81, 127.75, 127.70, 127.52, 77.44, 77.23, 77.02, 74.80, 74.73, 73.67, 73.55, 73.29, 72.79, 72.28, 71.89, 71.58, 70.86, 69.54, 69.35, 69.21, 69.06, 68.87, 68.28, 51.53, 37.08, 32.14, 30.25, 29.91, 29.58, 29.22, 28.79, 27.43, 23.62, 23.48, 23.31, 22.91, 22.22, 21.47, 21.21, 20.97, 20.89, 19.18, 14.34. ESI-MS: *m/z* calcd for (%). C₁₈₈H₁₉₆N₈O₆₄: 3589.23; found: 1818.6140 (M + Na)⁺²

A mixture of Compound **31** (92 mg, 26 μmol) and 10 mL mixture of ethylene diamine and *n*-butanol (1 : 4) was stirred at 90 °C overnight. The volatiles were evaporated, and the crude product was reacted with 10 mL mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine (1 : 2) overnight. The solvents were removed using high vacuum, and the product was purified by flash column chromatography (acetone : toluene, 2/8,v/v). The product was deacetylated using sodium methoxide in MeOH (10 mL) overnight. The reaction mixture was neutralized by using IR-120, then, filtered and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (acetone : toluene, 3/7,v/v). The product was dissolved in 10 mL MeOH : H₂O : HCOOH (6 : 3 : 1), Pd(OH)₂ (50% by weight) was added, and the reaction mixture was hydrogenated overnight, then filtered through Celite and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by Bio-Gel P-2 (BIO-RAD) column chromatography using water as eluent. The product was then lyophilized to get the the **AGC 1** (20 mg, 11.3 μmol , 44%) as white color powder. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, D₂O): δ 5.12 (s, 1H, 1-H), 4.85 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.2 Hz), 4.79 (s, 1H, 1-H), 4.68 (s, 1H, 1-H), 4.59 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 8.3 Hz), 4.53 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 2.4 Hz), 4.52 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 2.4 Hz), 4.48 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 7.8 Hz), 4.46 (d, 1H, 1-H, *J* = 7.8 Hz), 4.25 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 3.3 Hz), 4.23 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 3.0 Hz), 4.21 - 4.20 (m, 1H, Ring-H), 4.15 (d, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 10.3 Hz), 4.05 (dd, 1H, Ring-H, *J* = 9.3 Hz, *J* = 3.3 Hz), 4.00 - 3.98 (m, 1H,

Ring-H), 3.93 - 3.81 (m, 11H, Ring-H), 3.80 - 3.66 (m, 21H, Ring-H), 3.65 - 3.52 (m, 15H, Ring-H), 3.50 - 3.47 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.46-3.39 (m, 5H, Ring-H and CH₂), 3.31 - 3.28 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.97 (t, 2H, CH₂, *J* = 7.9 Hz), 2.07 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.06 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.06 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.04 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2.02 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 1.65 (q, 2H, CH₂, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 1.58 (q, 2H, CH₂, *J* = 6.7 Hz) 1.39 - 1.36 (m, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, D₂O): δ 174.92, 174.72, 174.55, 174.46, 174.40, 102.84, 101.60, 101.22, 101.02, 100.95, 100.92, 100.25, 99.67, 99.00, 81.68, 80.09, 79.20, 79.03, 78.33, 78.01, 76.32, 76.03, 75.79, 75.72, 75.66, 75.31 74.84, 74.76, 74.59, 74.46, 74.29, 73.37, 73.2, 72.42, 72.35, 72.12, 71.99, 71.87, 70.89, 70.12, 70.07, 69.90, 69.86, 68.50, 68.44, 68.07, 67.97, 67.24, 65.47, 61.47, 61.24, 61.00, 60.64, 60.02, 59.85, 55.47, 55.22, 55.11, 55.04, 54.96, 39.27, 28.01, 26.35, 22.61, 22.34, 22.12, 22.08, 22.05. ESI-MS: *m/z* calcd for ESI-MS: *m/z* calcd C₆₉H₁₁₉N₆O₄₆: 1768.7191; found: 1768.7225 (M + H)⁺.

Chapter 4 REFERENCES

- (1) (a) *Essentials of Glycobiology*; Varki, A., Cummings, R. D., Esko, J. D., Stanley, P., Hart, G. W., Aebi, M., Darvill, A. G., Kinoshita, T., Packer, N. H., Prestegard, J. H., Schnaar, R. L., Seeberger, P. H., Eds.; Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press: Cold Spring Harbor, NY, 1999. (b) Helenius, A.; Aebi, M. Exploring Glycans. *Cell* **2000**, *101* (2), 150-151. (c) Torreno-Pina, J. A.; Castro, B. M.; Manzo, C.; Buschow, S.I.; Cambi, A.; Garcia-Parajo, M. F. Enhanced receptor-clathrin interactions induced by *N*-glycan-mediated membrane micropatterning. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2014**, *111* (30), 11037-11042. (d) Leclaire, C.; Lecointe, K.; Gunning, P.A.; Tribolo, S.; Kavanaugh, D. W.; Wittmann, A.; Latousakis, D.; MacKenzie, D. A.; Kawasaki, N.; Juge, N. Molecular Basis for Intestinal Mucin Recognition by galectin-3 and C-type Lectins. *FASEB J.* **2018**, *32* (6), 3301-3320. (e) Kim, H.J.; Kim, S.C.; Ju, W.; Kim, Y.H.; Yin, S.Y.; Kim, H.J., Aberrant sialylation and fucosylation of intracellular proteins in cervical tissue are critical markers of cervical carcinogenesis. *Oncology Reports* 2014, *31*, 1417-1422.
- (2) (a) Rudd, P. M.; Dwek, R. A. Glycosylation: Heterogeneity and the 3D Structure of Proteins. *Crit. Rev. Biochem. Mol. Biol.* **1997**, *32* (1), 1-100. (b) Krasnova, L.; Wong, C.-H., Oligosaccharide Synthesis and Translational Innovation. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141* (9), 3735-3754.
- (3) (a) Wang, L. X.; Lomino, J. V. Emerging Technologies for Making Glycan-Defined Glycoproteins. *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2012**, *7*, 110–122. (b) An, H. J.; Froehlich, J. W.; Lebrilla, C. B. Determination of glycosylation sites and site-specific heterogeneity in glycoproteins. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2009**, *13* (4), 421-426.
- (4) (a) Shivatare, S. S.; Chang, S.-H.; Tsai, T.-I.; Ren, C.-T.; Chuang, H.-Y.; Hsu, L.; Lin, C.-W.; Li, S.-T.; Wu, C.-Y.; Wong, C.-H. Efficient Convergent Synthesis of Bi-, Tri-, and Tetra-antennary Complex Type *N*-Glycans and Their HIV-1 Antigenicity. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135* (41), 15382-15391. (b) Wang, G.; Zhang, W.; Lu, Z.; Wang, P.; Zhang, X.; Li, Y.; Wang, G.; Zhang, W.; Lu, Z.; Wang, P.; Zhang, X.; Li, Y. Convenient synthesis of an *N*-glycan octa-saccharide of the bisecting type. *J. Org. Chem.* **2009**, *74*, 2508–2515.
- (5) (a) Li, L.; Liu, Y.; Ma, C.; Qu, J.; Calderon, A. D.; Wu, B.; Wei, N.; Wang, X.; Guo, Y.; Xiao, Z.; Song, J.; Sugiarto, G.; Li, Y.; Yu, H.; Chen, X.; Wang, P. G. Efficient chemoenzymatic synthesis of an *N*-glycan isomer library. *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 5652. (b) Li, T.; Liu, L.; Wei, N.; Yang, J.-Y.; Chapla, D. G.; Moremen, K. W.; Boons, G.-J. An

-
- automated platform for the enzyme-mediated assembly of complex oligosaccharides. *Nat. Chem.* **2019**, *11*, 229–236. (c) Yang, W.; Ramadan, S.; Orwenyo, J.; Diaz, T. K. T.; Eken, Y.; Sanda, M.; Jackson, J. E.; Wilson, A. K.; Huang, X. F. Chemoenzymatic synthesis of glycopeptides bearing rare *N*-glycan sequences with or without bisecting GlcNAc. *Chem. Sci.* **2018**, *9* (43), 8194-8206.
- (6) Shivatare, S. S.; Chang, S.-H.; Tsai, T.-I.; Tseng, S.-Y.; Shivatare, V. S.; Lin, Y.-S.; Cheng, Y.-Y.; Ren, C.-T.; Lee, C.-C. D.; Pawar, S.; Tsai, C.-S.; Shih, H.-W.; Zeng, Y.-F.; Liang, C.-H.; Kwong, P. D.; Burton, D. R.; Wu, C.-Y.; Wong, C.-H. Modular synthesis of *N*-glycans and arrays for the hetero-ligand binding analysis of HIV antibodies. *Nat. Chem.* **2016**, *8* (4), 338–346.
- (7) Wang, Z.; Chinoy, Z. S.; Ambre, S. G.; Peng, W.; McBride, R. de Vries, R. P.; Glushka, J.; Paulson, J. C.; Boons, G. J. A General Strategy for the Chemoenzymatic Synthesis of Asymmetrically Branched *N*-Glycans. *Science*. **2013**, *341*, 379.
- (8) (a) Lo, H.-J.; Krasnova, L.; Dey, S.; Cheng, T.; Liu, H.; Tsai, T.-I.; Wu, K. B.; Wu, C.-Y.; Wong, C.-H. Synthesis of sialidase-resistant oligosaccharide and antibody glycoform containing α 2,6-linked 3FAx-Neu5Ac. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141* (16), 6484-6488. (b) Li, C.; Wang, L.-X. Chemoenzymatic Methods for the Synthesis of Glycoproteins. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 8359.
- (9) (a) Stevens, J.; Blixt, O.; Paulson, J. C.; Wilson, I. A. Glycan microarray technologies: tools to survey host specificity of influenza viruses. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **2006**, *4* (11), 857-864. (b) Blixt, O.; Head, S.; Mondala, T.; Scanlan, C.; Huflejt, M. E.; Alvarez, R.; Bryan, M. C.; Fazio, F.; Calarese, D.; Stevens, J.; Razi, N.; Stevens, D. J.; Skehel, J. J.; van Die, I.; Burton, D. R.; Wilson, I. A.; Cummings, R.; Bovin, N.; Wong, C. H.; Paulson, J. C. Printed covalent glycan array for ligand profiling of diverse glycan binding proteins. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2004**, *101*, 17033.
- (10) (a) Tsai, T.-I.; Lee, H.-Y.; Chang, S.-H.; Wang, C.-H.; Tu, Y.-C.; Lin, Y.-C.; Hwang, D. -R.; Wu, C.-Y.; Wong, C.-H. Effective sugar nucleotide regeneration for the large-scale enzymatic synthesis of globo H and SSEA4. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 14831–14839. (b) Kakuta, Y.; Okino, N.; Kajiwara, H.; Ichikawa, M.; Takakura, Y.; Ito, M.; Yamamoto, T. Crystal structure of vibronaceae photobacterium sp. JT-ISH-224 α 2,6-sialyltransferase in a ternary complex with donor product CMP and acceptor substrate lactose: catalytic mechanism and substrate recognition. *Glycobiology*. **2008**, *18* (1), 66–73.

(11) (a) Zhu, T.; Boons, G.-J. Intermolecular aglycon transfer of ethyl thioglycosides can be prevented by judicious choice of protecting groups. *Carbohydr. Res.* **2000**, 329, 709–715. (b) Reddy, G.V.; Jain, R. K.; Locke, R. D.; Matta, K. L. Synthesis of precursors for the dimeric 3-O-SO₃Na Lewis X and Lewis A structures. *Carbohydr. Res.* **1996**, 280, 261-276. (c) Xia, J.; Alderfer, J. L.; Locke, R. D.; Piskorz, C. F.; Matta, K. L. Complex oligosaccharide investigations: Synthesis of an octasaccharide incorporating the dimeric Lex structure of PSGL-1. *J. Org. Chem.* **2003**, 68 (7), 2752-2759. (d) Watabe, J.; Singh, L.; Nakahara, Y.; Ito, Y.; Hojo, H.; Nakahara, Y. Synthesis of core-class 2 O-Linked glycopeptides: a benzyl-protected tetrasaccharyl serine and its derivative carrying a hydrophobic cholestanyl group. *Biosci. Biotechnol. Biochem.* **2002**, 66(9), 1904-1914. (e) Takano, Y.; Kojima, N.; Nakahara, Y.; Hojo, H.; Nakahara, Y. Solid-phase synthesis of core 2 O-linked glycopeptide and its enzymatic sialylation. *Tetrahedron.* **2003**, 59(42), 8415-8427. (f) Jain, R. K.; Vig, R.; Locke, R. D.; Mohammad, A.; Matta, K. L. Selectin ligands: 2,3,4-tri-O-acetyl-6-O-pivaloyl- α/β -galactopyranosyl halide as novel glycosyl donor for the synthesis of 3-O-sialyl or 3-O-sulfo Lex and Lea type structures. *Chem. Commun.* **1996**, 65-67.

Chapter 5 LC-MS ANALYSIS DATA

Chart 3 LC and MS-MS of **AGC 1**.

A: LC retention time of **AGC 1**, B: MS-MS spectrum of **AGC 1**.

Chart 4 LC of enzymatic fucosylations.

A: LC retention time of FUT1 reaction, B: LC retention time of FUT6 reaction, C: LC retention time of FUT8 reaction. The FUT6 reaction showed a full conversion, but the FUT1 and FUT8 reactions did not achieve a full conversion of the starting material. Retention time unit: minute. Areas: relative integration of intensity.

Chart 5 MS-MS Spectra of enzymatic fucosylations.

A: MS-MS spectrum of FUT1 reaction, B: MS-MS spectrum of FUT6 reaction, C: MS-MS spectrum of FUT8 reaction. It was shown that the FUT8 product was lack of terminal fucose so the NHF fragment (the fragment of $m/z = 512$) did not appear in the spectrum, and the patterns of spectra of FUT1 and FUT6 reactions were different. Fragment structures were given by GlycoWorkbench2[®].

Chart 6 Comparison of MS3 between FUT1 and FUT6 product.

The spectra were the result from the fragmentation of $m/z = 512$ of FUT1 and FUT6 products. The $m/z = 168$ in the FUT1 product should be resulted from hexose though GlycoWorkbench2[®] did not show its prediction.

Chart 7 LC of enzymatic sialylations.

A: LC retention time of ST6Gal reaction, B: LC retention time of ST6Gal reaction.

Unit of retention time: minute. areas: relative integration of intensity.

Chart 8 MS-MS spectra of enzymatic sialylations.

A: MS-MS spectrum of ST3Gal reaction, B: MS-MS spectrum of ST6Gal reaction.

The spectra showed pattern differences between different sialylated compounds. Possible fragments resulted from the m/z analysis were shown. Fragment structures were given by GlycoWorkbench[®].

Chart 13 Comparison of MS3 between ST3Gal and ST6Gal product.

The spectra were resulted from the fragmentation of $m/z = 657$ of ST3Gal and ST6Gal products. The patterns of spectra of ST3Gal and ST6Gal reactions were different.

Appendix

5.04
4.77
4.60
4.51
4.50
4.47
4.46
4.45
4.44
4.40
4.39
4.35
4.34
4.16
4.12
4.07
4.05
3.98
3.96
3.89
3.88
3.84
3.82
3.81
3.79
3.74
3.73
3.71
3.69
3.68
3.67
3.64
3.62
3.61
3.60
3.56
3.53
3.51
3.50
3.48
3.47
3.45
3.41
3.37
3.35
3.32
3.30
3.23
3.21
2.87
2.85
2.58
2.58
2.56
2.01
1.98
1.97
1.96
1.93
1.63
1.61
1.59
1.57
1.55
1.54
1.50
1.49
1.48

**¹H NMR spectrum of ST6Gal product
(600MHz, D₂O, sialyl C3 peaks circled red)**

^{13}C NMR spectrum of ST6Gal product (600MHz, D_2O)

4.765
4.596
4.454
4.447
4.441
4.433
3.860
3.855
3.823
3.804
3.798
3.793
3.785
3.767
3.762
3.753
3.744
3.737
3.705
3.695
3.682
3.675
3.667
3.659
3.645
3.635
3.626
3.618
3.611
3.605
3.595
3.586
3.585
3.566
3.563
3.551
3.541
3.530
3.524
3.515
3.508
3.499
3.494
3.491
3.488
3.481
3.474
3.471
3.462
3.458
3.350
3.342
2.841
1.976
1.971
1.953
1.933
1.930

**¹H NMR spectrum of ST3Gal product
(600MHz, D₂O, sialyl C3 peaks circled red)**

¹³C NMR spectrum of ST6Gal product (600MHz),

**COSY NMR spectrum of ST6Gal product
(600MHz, D₂O)**

HSQC non-decoupled
NMR spectrum of compound 28

HSQC NMR spectrum of compound 29
(600MHz, CDCl₃)

HSQC NMR spectrum of compound 29
(600MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of compound 5 (600MHz, CDCl₃)

HMBC NMR spectrum of compound 5
(600MHz, CDCl₃)

